

**Impact of Human Resources on Productivity and Financial
Performance for Organizational Growth: A Comparative Study
on Selected Public and Private Organizations in Bangladesh**

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List of Acronym

HRM	Human Resources Management
BD	Bangladesh
FY	Financial Year
DESCO	Dhaka Electric Supply Company
BEXIMCO	Bangladesh Export Import Company
ACI	Advanced Chemical Industries

Impact of Human Resources on Productivity and Financial Performance for Organizational Growth: A Comparative Study on Selected Public and Private Organizations in Bangladesh

ABSTRACT

This research uncovers the impact of human resources on productivity and financial performances towards organizational growth. It allows comparative analyses and findings on Bangladeshi public and private organizations employees' contribution towards respective organizations. Basically, 180 employees (90 from public and 90 from private) have been considered as sample size to conduct this research. Randomly three public and three private organizations (namely; Petrobangla, Titas Gas & DESCO and ACI, BEXIMCO & SQUARE) have been selected to collect both primary and secondary data. Primary data have been collected through a structured questionnaire. Conversely, secondary data (last five consecutive years' financial statements) have been collected from the selected organizations. Mainly, descriptive statistics, multiple regression analysis, time series analysis have been used to analyze and interpret data. Hypotheses have been tested through multiple regression method using SPSS. The results show that organizational growth certainly depends on employees' productivity and financial performance for both public and private sector organizations. In addition, time series analyses have been undertaken using SPSS to know the current situation and forecast financial condition of public and private organizations for next five years. Results show that public organizations financial condition more vulnerable, there are huge ups and downs in the financial performances over the years. Next five years financial forecasting also suggests that consistent ups and downs will be there and government may have to subsidize consistently those organizations over the years. On the other hand time series data analyses result show that private organizations have been doing well in terms of their financial performances. Besides financial forecasting for the following five years also suggests that consistent upward trend to be found in terms of their financial activities. While conducting this research public organizations employee were reluctant to provide their responses, dissimilarly private organizations employees were found to be interested to response properly on the questionnaire survey by the researchers. Finally, this research can be evidence for the policymakers, researchers and private and public sector organizations toward realizing the significant impact of employees' contributions, involvement, and improvement of skills and financial growth of the organizations.

Keywords: Human Resources, Public Organizations, Private Organizations, Productivity, Financial Performance, Organizational Growth, Bangladesh.

Chapter: 1

**INTRODUCTION &
ORGANIZATIONS' PROFILE**

1.0 INTRODUCTION

A rapidly changing economic environment, characterized by such phenomena as the globalization and deregulation of markets, changing customer and investor demands, and ever-increasing product-market competition, has become the norm for most private and public organizations. To compete, they must continually improve their performance by reducing costs, innovating products and processes, and improving quality, productivity, and speed to market. With this Special Research on human resources and organizational performance, we hope to contribute to a better understanding of the role of human resources on productivity and financial performance for organizational growth.

The conceptual and empirical work relevant to this question has progressed far enough to suggest that the role of human resources can be crucial. However, given the importance and complexities of the issue, this body of work is relatively small, and most of the key questions are sorely in need of further attention. We hope that the publication of this special research will encourage and reinforce interest in this area, as well as help researchers in their decisions regarding what to study and how to study it. We also hope that it will demonstrate to senior human resources (HR) and line managers that their HR systems represent a largely untapped opportunity to improve performance of employees both public and private services in Bangladesh.

How do human resource decisions influence organizational productivity and financial performance? In the simplest terms, they must either improve efficiency or contribute to financial growth. Human resources, both as employees and as a business function, have traditionally been viewed as a cost to be minimized and a potential source of efficiency gains by both public and private organizations. Very seldom have HR decisions been considered a source of value creation, or what termed “numerator management”. Labor costs continue to be the single largest operating cost in many organizations, and reductions in employment continue to be a major aspect of strategies to restructure operations and reduce these costs. Do these decisions create value, or just reduce costs? Empirically, the challenge is to distinguish between staffing reductions that are purely cost-cutting measures and restructurings that require fewer employees but create value because the new structures are more appropriate for the firms’ particular strategies.

In Bangladesh human resources usually have merely been seen to be trained and cared properly both in public and private sector organizations though private organizations sometimes try to improve skills and efficiency of the employees. The organizational structures, cultures, norms, values, working environment, monitoring, responsibility, authority and so on vary between public and private organizations. Besides, many public organizations do not have to show interest on profit making rather trying to welfare of the people as per policy of the state. Conversely, private organizations prime concern is to make maximum profit through increasing amount of production and sales. According to their aims and operations employees’ efficiency, skills, affordability employees have been treated

differently. Therefore, productivity and financial performances of public and private organizations vary which also affect organizational growth.

1.1 Profile of the Organizations: Public Organizations

Petrobangla

Bangladesh Minerals, Oil and Gas Corporation (BMOGC) was established pursuant to President's Order no. 27 of 26 March, 1972 for dealing with the exploration and development of oil, gas and mineral resources of the country. The activities of the Corporation relating to minerals was segregated and placed under a new organization named Bangladesh Mineral Exploration and Development Corporation (BMEDC) formed by President's Order no. 120 of 27 September, 1972. The reconstituted Bangladesh Oil and Gas Corporation (BOGC) was short-named "Petrobangla" by Ordinance no. XV of 22 August, 1974. Through the repeal of Ordinance no: LXX of 1974, Oil and Gas Development Corporation were abolished and all its assets and liabilities were vested in Petrobangla. On 13 November, 1976, by promulgation of the Ordinance # 88, the import, refining and marketing of crude and petroleum products were separated and vested with the newly-formed Bangladesh Petroleum Corporation (BPC).

BOGC and BMEDC were merged into a single entity under the name "Bangladesh Oil, Gas and Mineral Corporation (BOGMC)" by Ordinance no. 21 of 11 April, 1985. The Corporation was short named "Petrobangla" and given power in Act XI of February, 1989 to hold shares or interest in any company formed for the purpose of exploration and exploitation of oil, gas and mineral resources.

Before 1947:

The search for oil and gas in the area constituting Bangladesh began in the later part of the 19th century through some isolated geological mapping. The first serious attempt to find oil and gas was undertaken in Sitakund in 1908 by the Indian Petroleum Prospecting Company, 18 years after the first oil discovery in Digboi, Assam. During 1923-31 Burmah Oil Company (BOC) drilled two shallow wells in Patharia. The wells were abandoned though there was a reported show of oil. A total of 6 exploratory wells were drilled, the deepest being 1047 meters. There was, however, no discovery and the Second World War disrupted further activities.

The interim: 1948 to 1971

The promulgation of Petroleum Act in 1948 generated a lot of interest in oil and gas exploration by international oil companies. The Standard Vacuum Oil Company (STANVAC) of USA, Pakistan Petroleum Ltd. (PPL), Burmah Oil Company affiliate and Pakistan Shell Oil Company (PSOC) carried out exploration till the end of the sixties. STANVAC drilled 3 wells at Hazipur, Bogra and Kuchma in the north-western part of the country without success. PPL drilled wells in Haripur, Patharia, Chhatak, Fenchuganj, Patiya and Lalmai and made the first gas discovery in Haripur in 1955, followed by Chattak in 1959. PSOC was the most successful company and discovered 5 gas fields named Titas, Habiganj, Rashidpur, Kailashtila and Bakhrabad. They also drilled the first offshore well Cox's Bazar-1, which was dry.

Oil and Gas Development Corporation (OGDC) was established in 1961 providing an institutional foundation for exploration of oil and gas in the country. OGDC carried out geological and geophysical surveys including gravity, magnetic and seismic types and drilled wells in Jaldi and Semutang, discovering gas in Semutang in 1970.

The way forward: 1972 to 1979

After the independence of Bangladesh, exploration activities by both national and international companies gathered pace. Bangladesh Oil, Gas and Mineral Corporation (Petrobangla) continued its exploration efforts while the Bangladesh Petroleum Act was passed in 1974 to facilitate international participation under Production Sharing Contract (PSC). The offshore area of Bangladesh was divided into 6 blocks, which were taken up by Ashland, ARCO, BODC (Japex), Union Oil, Canadian Superior Oil and Ina Naftaplin under PSCs. These companies carried out gravity, magnetic and seismic surveys (about 32,000 km) and drilled 7 wells. Of them, only Union Oil Company discovered an offshore gas field Kutubdia in 1977. This phase of PSC ended in relinquishment of the blocks by the PSC operators in 1978. On 9 August, 1975, Government led by the Father of the Nation Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman purchased five gas fields, namely Titas, Habiganj, Rashidpur, Kailashtila and Bakhrabad from British company, Shell Petroleum Company Limited, for a nominal amount of 4.5 million pound sterling. This landmark decision taken by the then Government laid the foundation of energy security of the country by introducing sole ownership of the state over these major gas fields.

Gathering momentum: 1980 onwards

The 1980s saw accelerated exploration activities by Petrobangla. During the time, 12 exploration wells were drilled at Muladi, Begumganj, Singra, Beanibazar, Atgram, Feni, Fenchuganj, Sitakund, Bogra, Kamta, Marichakandi (Meghna) and Belabo (Narshindi); and 7 gas fields were discovered at Begumganj, Beanibazar, Feni, Fenchuganj, Kamta, Marichakandi (Meghna) and Belabo (Narshindi). Among these, Fenchuganj # 2 well remains

the deepest one drilled so far in Bangladesh (4,977m). Meanwhile, a new milestone was achieved when Petrobangla discovered the first commercial oil pool in Sylhet # 7 on 23 December, 1986. Since 1989, after the formation of BAPEX as the national exploration company and thereafter exploration and production company, the company has continued exploration and production activities and drilled 4 exploratory wells discovering gas at Shahbazzpur, Saldanadi, Srikail and Sundalpur.

In 1981 Shell Oil Company (Shell) was awarded the Chittagong Hill Tracts for petroleum exploration under PSC. Shell conducted geological and seismic survey and drilled the Sitapahar well which was dry. Subsequently Shell undertook exploration in the extreme North West of the country and drilled the first well in the area - the Salbanhat well which was also dry. In 1988 Scimitar Exploration Limited was awarded another PSC of what is now block # 13 in the Surma basin. They failed to prove the extent of the oil discovery at Sylhet structure but discovered the Jalalabad gas field.

Formulation of National Energy Policy, 1996 and adoption of a model production sharing contract (PSC) document together with redefining the whole of Bangladesh territory into 23 exploration blocks ushered in a new phase of exploration and development of oil and gas in the country. In the first stage under the new arrangement, 8 blocks were awarded to 4 companies under PSC. Exploration and development activities in these blocks were rather limited and most of the blocks were moderately covered by seismic surveys. A total of 11 exploration wells were drilled and 3 gas fields were discovered in these blocks. These fields are Moulavibazar, Sangu (offshore) and Bibiyana. These 3 fields alongwith Jalalabad gas field discovered by Scimitar Exploration Ltd. were developed under PSC and are currently in production. The first 3D seismic survey of the country took place in Bibiyana during its appraisal. Bibiyana came under production in March, 2007. Another PSC bidding round during the late nineties culminated in awarding 4 more blocks. These were SHELL/CAIRN/BAPEX in blocks # 5 and 10, UNOCAL/BAPEX in block # 7 and TULLOW/ CHEVRON/TAXACO/BAPEX in block # 9. Exploration activity was conducted in these blocks. Substantial activities were undertaken in block # 9 only, where 5 exploration wells were drilled on the basis of seismic survey including 3D seismic.

The Offshore Bidding Round 2008 being limited to newly-formed deep water blocks, attracted some bids. However, the ensuing maritime boundary dispute in most of the blocks created a stalemate. In this backdrop, two blocks were negotiated with Conoco Phillips and a PSC for two blocks was signed in 2011. Conoco Phillips completed the initial seismic survey in the blocks. They relinquished these blocks in 2014 without drilling any exploratory well.

After the resolution of the Maritime boundary dispute with Myanmar by virtue of the judgment awarded on 14 March, 2012 by International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea (ITLOS), the deep water blocks on the eastern part were rearranged. This is a widely acclaimed achievement of the Government led by Hon`ble Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina. The Bangladesh Offshore Bid Round 2012 was announced in December, 2012 and substantial initial response was received. Under this Bid round, three shallow water PSCs have been signed with ONGC Videsh, Oil India & BAPPEX for blocks SS-04 and SS-09 and Santos, Kris Energy and BAPPEX for block SS-11. Deep water bids, received in January, 2014, are now being processed. Since the signing of the PSC's, several changes in ownership and restructuring in the contracts have taken place. All of the onshore PSC's have matured from the exploration phase to the production phase and major areas of the blocks have been relinquished. As of December, 2014 PSC's are active in production areas of blocks 12, 13 and 14 (Bibiyana, Jalalabad and Maulavibazar Gas Fields) operated by Chevron.

Even though exploration history of oil and gas in Bangladesh goes back almost a century, exploration density could not be enhanced as much it is required to convert domestic oil and gas resources into proven reserves. However, the exploration success ratio is high as of about 1 in 3 wells. PSC explorations were also contributing to the enhancement of gas production. As of December, 2014 out of 26 gas fields discovered, 19 were under production. Meanwhile, peak gas production per day crossed the level of 2,600 MMCFD wherein average daily gas production remained more than 2,500 MMCFD by December, 2014. Despite increase in production, the rising demand could not be met and the gap between supply and demand is widening. As such the government has taken steps to import LNG to minimize the gap.

Minerals:

Petrobangla is also entrusted with mineral development in the country. While the exploration part of minerals activity falls under the charter of Geological Survey of Bangladesh (GSB), subsequent development of economic deposits are undertaken by Petrobangla. Mineral activities were part of the erstwhile Bangladesh Mineral Exploration and Development Corporation (BMEDC) till its merger with BOGMC. Petrobangla has developed two underground mines, one for coal at Barapukuria which started commercial production in September, 2005 and the other for Granite at Maddhapara which went into commercial production in May, 2007. Certain other extraction operation, like limestone, white clay and boulder, are controlled by the government through the Bureau of Mineral Development (BMD).

Source: <https://www.petrobangla.org.bd>

Titas Gas

Name of the Company : Titas Gas Transmission & Distribution Company Limited (TGTDCCL)

Date of Incorporation : November 20, 1964

Registered Office: Titas Gas Bhaban, 105 Kazi Nazrul Islam Avenue, Kawran Bazar Commercial Area, Dhaka-1215.

Corporation: Bangladesh Oil, Gas & Mineral Corporation (Petrobangla)

Administrative Ministry : Ministry of Power, Energy & Mineral Resources

Titas Franchise Area: Greater Dhaka and Greater Mymensingh

First Constructed Pipeline: Brahmanbaria to Demra 14" DN X100 PSIG X 58 Miles

First Gas Supply: April 28, 1968 to Siddhirganj Thermal Power Station

Authorised Capital: Tk. 2,000.00 crore

Paid up Capital (As on June 30, 2018): Tk. 989.22 crore

Gas sales (FY 2017-18): 16,961.75 MMCM

Sales Revenue (FY 2017-18): TK.14,037.55 crore

Payment to the National Exchequer: TK. 558.47 crore

Number of Customers (As on June 30, 2018): Total 27,83,134

Power (Govt.): 08 NOS

Power (Private): 36 NOS

Fertilizer: 03 NOS

Industry: 5,128 NOS

CNG: 382 NOS

Captive Power: 1,630 NOS

Commercial: 11,688 NOS

Domestic: 27,64,247 NOS

Constructed Pipeline (As on June 30, 2018): 13,074.78 km

Market Share in Sales: 61%

Source of Gas supply (Fields): Titas, Habiganj, Narsingdi, Kailashtila, Bibiyana, Moulvi Bazar, Srikyl & Bangura Gas Fields.

Manpower (As on June 30, 2018): 2,282

Officer: 937

Staff: 1,345

Chief Executive: Md. Mostafa Kamal

Listed with DSE: June 9, 2008

Listed with CSE: June 19, 2008

The discovery of a huge gas field on the bank of the Titas River in Bhramanbaria in 1962 created a new horizon for the utilization of natural gas. Being established on November 20, 1964 Titas Gas Transmission and Distribution Company Limited (TGTDC) has completed 50 years of its operation. The company began its commercial operation with the commissioning of gas supply to Siddhirganj Thermal Power Station on April 28, 1968 after construction of 14 inch dia 58 mile long Titas-Demra gas pipeline by the then East Pakistan Industrial Development Corporation. As a progressive national organization, it has earned the glory of being a trustworthy one for the people by means of the quality of service delivery

Source: <https://www.titasgas.org.bd>

DESCO

The electricity supply industry in South Asia started with the commissioning of the first power station in the 1890s. Although a number of small stations were constructed over the next 20 years, these stations were isolated, catering to small distribution networks serving the major urban centers.

The first effort to structure a legal framework for the industry came in 1910 with the enactment of the Indian Electricity Act, 1910. This Act sought to regulate the business of industry still based on the old concept of isolated privately owned distribution networks fed by small generation stations & essentially defined the rights & obligations of the supplier and the consumer.

In 1947, at the time of independence of India & Pakistan, the installed generating capacity in the then East Pakistan was only 21 MW. Electricity was available to only a small elite in the district and sub-divisional headquarters. The distribution networks in these cities were isolated and were fed by coal fired steam power plants or diesel generation. In an effort to expeditiously augment generation capacity to feed a development economy, the then Government of Pakistan issued an ordinance in 1959 creating the East Pakistan Water and Power Development Authority (EWAPDA). The Ordinance essentially provided for the Government's takeover of all generation, Transmission and distribution facilities from the private sector, thereby creating a total Government monopoly in the sector. During 1960 to 1970 the generation capacity of the then East Pakistan rose from 88MW to 475 MW, supplied largely by natural gas and oil fired, steam power and hydro plants. The networks of Dhaka and Chittagong and then been interconnected albeit with weak 132 KV links.

Shortly after the creation of an independent Bangladesh, in 1972, the first Government of Bangladesh, in an effort to speed up the investment in the sector issued an Ordinance creating the Bangladesh Power Development Board (BPDB) as the successor organization of the power side of EWAPDA. The Ordinance recognized the divergence of energy related issues in development. During 1972 to 1995, BPDB has increased the generating capacity in the country to 2818 MW, and the length of its 230 and 132 KV transmission networks to 419 KM and 2469 KM. For the first time in December 1982, the eastern and western halves of the country were electrically connected through the commissioning of double circuit 230 KV transmission line across the Jamuna river energized at 132 KV between Ishurdi and Tongi called the first East-West Interconnector. Generation sources were diversified to include a 230 MW hydropower station at Kaptai on the Karnaphuli river and natural gas and imported fuel based, open and combined cycle power plants at different locations of Eastern and Western part of the country. The distribution networks of all major towns and cities had been linked through 230 KV and 132 KV inter-ties.

In order to intensify the pace of rural electrification, the Government issued an ordinance in 1977 establishing the Rural Electrification Board (REB), a semi-autonomous agency charged with the responsibility of planning, developing, financing and construction of rural distribution networks, promoting the establishment of Rural Electric Cooperatives (Palli Bidyut Samities), handing over the constructed rural networks to them, assisting the REBs to operate and maintain the rural networks and monitoring their financial performance. The REB has so far constructed over 46,000 Km of distribution lines and provided over 950,000 consumers connections in the rural areas.

In 1990, another ordinance was issued, which was subsequently enacted as an Act transferring the 132 kv, 33 kv Transmission and distribution system in the Greater Dhaka Area including the Metropolitan City to a newly created Government agency called the Dhaka Electric supply Authority (DESA). This was done to lessen the administrative burden on BPDB's management by relieving it of the burden of managing about 50 percent of the energy distribution in the entire country.

The Reform Process

Although several ordinances amending the Electricity Act, 1910 had been promulgated, none of them addressed issues involving the commercial nature of the sector, which continued to be treated as an extension of the Government providing social goods for the people. From 1986 onwards, the commercial performance of the BPDB deteriorated and during 1991, BPDB's average gross systems loss was about 42 percent and accounts receivables in excess of 6.5 months of billing. This performance was not found reasonable to the covenants agreed by the Government and BPDB with the Asian Development Bank and the World Bank. These two institutions along with the Overseas Economic Co-operation Fund, Japan, Overseas Development Administration, U. K., Kreditanstalt fur Wiederaufbau, Germany and the United States Agency for International Development, decided not to provide any financial assistance to the sector until BPDB and DESA improved their performance to agreed levels.

Consequently it considered restructuring the Power sector as a sustainable long-term solution to its problems.

With the economy performing very well during 1992-95, the demand for electricity grew substantially. Constrained by the paucity of its resources, the Government decided to allow private sector participation in the power sector. However, it was quickly realized that private capital, whether domestic or foreign, would not come into a sector, which was not financially viable and was not technically, organizationally and legally structured in a way conducive to attract it. Faced with a grim possibility of serious electricity shortages during the next few years and to enable the sector to be financially self-sustaining and also attract private capital, the cabinet approved in principle, the inter-ministerial committee report named "Power Sector Reforms in Bangladesh (PSRB)", in September 1994.

In the meanwhile, the performance of BPDB and DESA have slowly but steadily improved, although they are by no means near international levels of performance. In view of this Improvement and the restructuring effort announced by the Government, the development partners have agreed to resume funding to the sector based on the principle of "Reforms Fundina Linkaaes" i.e. every project funded by these partners would have components addressing the reforms decided upon by the Government. The first such project was the Rural Electrification Project of the ADB which was approved by the ADB,s Board on 30 May, 1995. This project resulted in the creation of the first independent generating company, incorporated under the companies Act 1994 in the power sector, with private sector capital from five Palli Biddut Samities. The project also developed model commercial transactions between the generator and the purchaser and the generator and the fuel supplier. This project is being followed up by likely financing of projects by the OECF (Haripur Extension) and kfw (Comilla-Chittagong Transmission Line).

The next candidate project of the reform process is the proposed Ninth Power Project financed by the ADB. This project comprises of four components.

- Transmission lines and substation capacity associated with the first 600 MW development stage of the Meghnaghat combined Cycle Power Project.
- Construction of National Control Centre and associated communication network.
- Construction of new and reinforcement of 132 kv, 33 kv, 11 kv and 0.4 kv distribution lines and transformation capacity in Dhaka City.
- Engineering of the West Zone Combined Cycle Power Project and the East Zone Open Cycle peaking Power Project.

As part of the "Reforms-Funding" linkage agreed between the development partners and the Government, the implementation of Part (C) of the Project has been linked to redefining the franchise area of DESA and handing over of distribution networks outside Metropolitan Dhaka City to PBS,s under REB, and formation of a corporatized Dhaka Electric Supply company (DESCO) which will initially take over part of the distribution network of DESA and ultimately take over all its assets. The formation of this company is seen as an essential step towards "corporatization and commercialization" of the sector and to reduce the

excessive inefficiently in the distribution network in the capital. This Project Proforma seeks the Government's approval for (i) part (b) of the ADB's proposed Ninth Power and Tenth Power Projects as detailed herein: ii The creation of the Dhaka Electric Su I Com an and iii Rationalization of the boundaries between DESA/DESCO and the PBSs.

The Project

A. Description of the Project (for DESA area only)

- Land Development
- Civil works
- 132 kv overhead line
- 132 kv U/G cable
- 33 kv O/H line
- 33 kv U/G line
- Construction of 132/33/11 KV S/S Construction of 32/11 KV S/S
- 11 KV O/H line
- 11/0.4 KV O/H line
- 400 V O/H line
- 11 KV UIG cable
- Pole Mounted S/S
- L T Meters (Single Phase)
- L T Meters (Three Phase)
- HT Meters (Three Phase) TransportNehicle (Different type)
- 10.85 Acres 17253.00 m2
- 31.00 Ckt. km. 15.00 Ckt. km. 43.00 Ckt. km. 71.50 Ckt. km. 8.00 Nos.
- 16.00 Nos.
- 150.00 Ckt. km. 500.00 Ckt. km. 600.00 Ckt. km. 400.00 Ckt. km. 3,000 Nos.
- 2,00,000 Nos. 34,000 Nos. 1 ,000 Nos. 48 Nos.

B. Description of the Project Under DESCO (Including Gulshan)

- Construction of 33/11 KV new S/S
- R & R of existing 33/11 KV S/S 33 KV U/G Cable
- 11 KV Circuit Breaker
- 11 KV O/H line
- 11/0.4 KV O/H line
- 400 Volts O/H line
- 2 Nos. 4 Nos.
- 44 Ckt. km. 46 Nos.
- 120 Ckt. km. 100 Ckt. km. 100 Ckt. km.
- 11 KV UIG Cable
- 11 KV Aerial Cable 100 Volts UIG Cable 400 Volts Aerial Cables Single Phase Meter
- L T Meter (Three Phase) HT Meter
- 20 Ckt. km.
- 5 Ckt. km. 5 Ckt. km. 5 Ckt. km.

- 20,000 Nos. 5,000 Nos. 100 Nos.

Source: <https://www.desco.org.bd>

1.2 Profile of the Organizations: Private Organizations

ACI

Imperial Chemical Industries, a British multinational established a Branch in the then East Pakistan which was converted into a company after liberation, named ICI Bangladesh Manufacturers Limited. In 1992 ICI divested its investment in Bangladesh to the Management, when its name was changed to Advanced Chemical Industries (ACI) Limited. It is being one of the largest conglomerates in Bangladesh with a multinational heritage operates across the country through its four diversified strategic business units. 'ACI Pharmaceuticals' is dedicated to improve the health of people of Bangladesh through introduction of innovative and reliable Pharmaceuticals products.

'ACI Consumer Brands' is adding value to the daily life of consumers through its Toiletries, Home care, Hygiene, Electrical, Electronics, Mobile, Salt, Flour, Foods, Rice, Tea, Edible Oil, Paints and International businesses. 'ACI Agribusinesses' is the largest integrator in Bangladesh in Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries, Farm Mechanization, Infrastructure Development Services and Motorcycles. 'ACI Retail Chain' is the largest retail chain in the country operating through its 73 SHWAPNO outlets across the country by touching the lives of over 35,000 households each day. The company contributed Taka 3,625 million to the National Exchequer during FY 2017-2018 in the form of corporate tax, custom duty and value added tax.

Basic Information

Full Name: Advanced Chemical Industries Ltd.

Incorporation Date: 24 January 1973

Registration No: C-3885

Company Type: Public Limited

Number of employees: 9,053

Authorized capital: 1,500,000,000

Issued and paid capital: 49,88,95,270

No of Shares: 49,889,527

Face Value: 10

Year End: 30 June

Source: <http://www.aci-bd.com>

BEXIMCO

Today the BEXIMCO Group ("BEXIMCO" or the "Group") is the largest private sector group in Bangladesh. BEXIMCO was founded in the 1970's by two brothers – Ahmed Sohail Fasiur Rahman and Salman Fazlur Rahman. Since the early days, the Group has evolved from being primarily a commodities trading company to a leading, diversified group with a presence in industry sectors that account for nearly 75% of Bangladesh's GDP. BEXIMCO's corporate mission is "Taking Bangladesh to the world".

As BEXIMCO has grown over the years, the flagship platform now has operations and investments across a wide range of industries including textiles, trading, marine food, real estate development, hospitality, construction, information and communication technologies, media, ceramics, aviation, pharmaceuticals, financial services and energy. The Group sells its products and services in the domestic Bangladesh market as well as international markets. BEXIMCO is the largest employer in the private sector in Bangladesh and employs over 70,000 people worldwide.

The BEXIMCO name has now become one of the most recognizable brand names in Bangladesh. It is synonymous with innovation, trust and quality. The Group consists of four publicly traded and seventeen privately held companies. The publicly traded companies – Bangladesh Export Import Company Limited, Beximco Pharmaceuticals Limited, Shinepukur Ceramics Limited and Beximco Synthetics Limited – have a combined market capitalization of approximately \$617.34 million. The Group had total revenues of \$834 million in the year ended December 31, 2010.

BEXIMCO encompasses one of South Asia's largest vertically integrated textile and garment companies. The Textile division is a fully integrated manufacturer of cotton and polyester blended garments for men, women and children, both for domestic and export markets. BEXIMCO is also the largest exporter of pharmaceuticals in Bangladesh with a presence in 45 countries. The Pharmaceuticals division manufactures and sells generic pharmaceutical formulation products, active pharmaceutical ingredients (API) and intravenous (IV) fluids. The Group is also the largest ceramics exporter in Bangladesh.

State-of-the-art manufacturing plants located in the vicinity of Dhaka provide the Group with a highly cost effective manufacturing base. A majority of its plants are in the BEXIMCO Industrial Park, a vertically integrated self-contained facility. This facility provides ready access to captive power generation, water purification, liquid nitrogen, waste water treatment and other key infrastructure. The Group's global clients include some of the world's best known brands including BT, Chevron, Calvin Klein, H&M, JC Penney, Macys, Zara, UNICEF, Royal Doulton and Villeroy & Boch.

BEXIMCO is well positioned to capitalize on strong growth across industries in both the domestic and global markets. Each Group company is managed by an independent, professional team with significant depth of experience. Management teams have established a clear strategic plan that will further strengthen the overall platform. BEXIMCO intends to leverage its market position and global scale, further diversify operations into highly profitable sectors, capitalize on the domestic growth opportunity and selectively pursue international opportunities going forward.

In recognition of its corporate success and creation of shareholder value, the BEXIMCO Group has and continues to make significant contributions to Bangladesh's society. Sponsored organizations include "Proyash", a specialized institute that works for the holistic development of children with special educational needs and "Gono Sahajjo Songstha", an institution that provides education for the underprivileged. BEXIMCO was also an official sponsor of the Bangladesh National Cricket team for the ICC Cricket World Cup 2011 and also the official title sponsor of the FIFA friendly match between Argentina and Nigeria held in September, 2011.

Source: <https://www.beximco.com>

SQUARE today symbolizes a name – a state of mind. But its journey to the growth and prosperity has been no bed of roses. From the inception in 1958, it has today burgeoned into one of the top line conglomerates in Bangladesh. Square Pharmaceuticals Ltd., the flagship company, is holding the strong leadership position in the pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh since 1985 and is now on its way to becoming a high performance global player.

SQUARE today is more than just an organization, it is an institute. In a career spanning across four and half decades it has pioneered the development of the local business in fields as diverse as Pharmaceuticals, Toiletries, Garments, Textile, Information Technology, Health Products, Food Products, Hospital, etc. With an average Annual turnover of over US\$ 200 million and a workforce of about 3500 the SQUARE Group is a true icon of the Bangladesh business sector.

Source: http://www.e-home2u.com/about_square_group.php

Chapter: 2
LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Since there is limited sources of data available in this field of study especially in Bangladesh this is why a number of scholars' published articles, research papers, thesis paper, project reports and a number of different countries related websites will be studied and cited in this study. Following are the related literatures which have been reviewed primarily for this study:

According to Markovits, Y. et al. (2007) examined that the affective organizational commitment was found to be most influential with respect to levels of intrinsic and extrinsic job satisfaction. This concurs with other studies of the behavioral outcomes of commitment. **Adamchik, V A., and Arjun S. B. (2000)** claimed that there were wage differentials between workers in the public and the private sectors. After standardizing for worker characteristics and sector selection effects, they found that a private sector wage advantage. The wage premium was particularly pronounced for university educated workers. Their results suggested that these wage differentials would make it difficult for the public sector to attract and retain skilled employees. In addition, lower public sector wages might encourage moonlighting and compromise the efficiency of the public sector. **Markovits, Y. et al. (2010)** suggested that attitudes toward job and organizations, and relationships between private and public sectors, were different. They examined that the satisfaction-commitment link with respect to differences between private and public sector employees. Their results confirmed the hypothesized relationship differences: Extrinsic satisfaction and intrinsic satisfaction were more strongly related to affective commitment and normative commitment for public sector employees than for private sector ones.

Lyons, S. T. et al. (2006) revealed that private employees value work that contributes to society more than public servants, who value it more than private sector employees; private employees value opportunities for advancement less than both public and private sector employees; public servants value intellectually stimulating and challenging work more than private organizations employees; and private sector employees value prestigious work more than public servants. Private sector employees displayed greater organizational commitment than the employees in the other two sectors. Overall, the findings suggested that only limited value differences among employees of the various sectors. **Buelens, M. and Herman V. d. B. (2007)** described that differences in hierarchical level were more important determinants of work motivation than sectoral differences. In addition, most observed differences could be wholly or partially explained by differences in job content, not by the sector itself. Evidence was presented to show that motivational differences could be explained by a positive choice of work-life balance. **Bellante, D. and Albert N. L. (1981)** found that Available evidence suggests that stability of employment is greater in the public sector than in the private sector. The value that individuals place on this stability depends on the individual's degree of risk aversion. Economic reasoning suggests that, other things equal, those individuals with a high degree of aversion to risk will be more likely than others to seek employment in the public sector. This paper tests that hypothesis through the use of profit analysis and a measure of risk aversion developed in the University of Michigan's Panel Study of Income Dynamics. The results tend to confirm the hypothesis, implying that a policy of intersectoral equality of pay for comparable jobs would result in an excess supply of workers to the public sector. **Tsigilis, N. et al. (2006)** studied that One hundred and seventy eight childhood educators participated in the study. 108 were working in the public sector, 67 in private sector, whereas three did not respond. Results showed that early educators experienced moderate levels of

emotional exhaustion. Public sector early educators were more satisfied from the job itself and their immediate supervisor than their counterparts in the private sector. Regression analysis showed that job satisfaction facets which contributed to early educators' burnout varied as a function of their workplace. In particular, satisfaction from the nature of the job and working conditions negatively contributed to the prediction of public sector early educators' emotional exhaustion levels. On the other hand, increased levels of satisfaction from the nature of the job and immediate supervisor were associated with reduced private sector early educators' emotional exhaustion levels.

Manzoor, Q. A. (2012) built three hypotheses based on the literature and the model and were tested in perspective of the previous studies and literature. Empowerment and recognition have positive effect on employee motivation. More the empowerment and recognition of employees in an organization is increased, more will their motivation to work will enhance. Also there exists a positive relationship between employee motivation and organizational effectiveness. The more the employees are motive to tasks accomplishment higher will the organizational performance and success. The organizations should design their rules, policies and organizational structures that give space to the employee to work well and appreciate them on their tasks fulfillment and achievements. This will surely lead to organizational growth. **Singh, J. (2000)** analyzed to understand mechanisms that govern the productivity and quality of frontline employees (FLEs). this study (1) provides a conceptual distinction between frontline productivity and quality, (2) proposes an extended role theory-based model for mapping the influence of key antecedents and consequences of FLE productivity and quality, and (3) examines the effects of coping resources—boss support and task control in helping employees cope with the inherent productivity-quality tension in frontline jobs. Hypotheses through multiple-group path analysis the results indicate support for the distinction between productivity and quality. Moreover, with increasing burnout levels FLEs are found to maintain their productivity levels while their quality deteriorates directly. Relative to boss support, task control emerges as a more powerful resource in aiding FLEs in coping with role tension.

Huselid, M. A. (1995) evaluated the links between systems of High Performance Work Practices and firm performance. Results based on a national sample of nearly one thousand firms indicate that these practices have an economically and statistically significant impact on both intermediate employee outcomes (turnover and productivity) and short- and long-term measures of corporate financial performance. Support for predictions that the impact of High Performance Work Practices on firm performance is in part contingent on their interrelationships and links with competitive strategy was limited. **Bartel, A. P. (1994)** uncovered that training plays a crucial role to increase employees' performance and organizational productivity. He found that higher rate of productivity one of the key factors of employees' consistent training other than administrative policies. **Gruman, J. A. and Alan M. S. (2011)** suggest that producing performance increments may be best achieved by orienting the performance management system to promote employee engagement. To this end, we describe a new approach to the performance management process that includes employee engagement and the key drivers of employee engagement at each stage. We present a model of engagement management that incorporates the main ideas of the paper and suggests a new perspective for thinking about how to foster and manage employee engagement to achieve high levels of job performance. **Leblebici, D. (2012)** established

agreed the workplace environment plays a crucial role for the employees. Nowadays employees may have a large number working alternatives, and then the environment in workplace becomes a critical factor for accepting and/or keeping the jobs. The quality of environment in workplace may simply determine the level of employee's motivation, subsequent performance and productivity. This paper presents the analysis of working environment of a foreign private bank in Turkey and examines the relationship between the workplace physical conditions and employee's productivity.

Konrad, A. M., and Robert M. (2000) examined the adoption of work-life programs and the impact of work-life programs on firm productivity. Productivity data were obtained from CD Disclosure for 195 public, for-profit firms. Significant interaction effects indicated that in these 195 firms work-life programs had a stronger positive impact on productivity when women comprised a larger percentage of the workforce and when a higher percentage of professionals were employed. **Samnani, A. k. and P. S. (2014)** suggested that performance-enhancing compensation practices are designed to increase employee productivity through greater accountability, while highlighting performance differentials across employees. While productivity increases may occur, these practices can also stimulate an unintended consequence: workplace bullying. In this paper, we present a typology and conceptual model that explore the boundary conditions under which performance-enhancing compensation practices may result in bullying behavior with differential effects on target and perpetrator productivity. We propose the mediating roles of individual competition and stress between zero-sum pay systems and workplace bullying. In our model, we propose that perpetrators will realize increased productivity. **Obisi, C. (2011)** expounded that organizational performance and its resultant efficiency and effectiveness can only be achieved when individuals are continuously appraised and evaluated. The inability of organization to install an effective performance appraisal strategy has hindered them from achieving competitive advantage which they require more now than ever before. Organizations should stop giving less attention to the evaluation of their employees and recognize that organizational training needs can only be identified from performance appraisal outcomes. It is an invaluable tool but in the hands of human resource management officers to continuously evaluates and audits the performance of its employees in other to help organizations win competitive advantage. **Elnaga, A. and Amen I. (2013)** found that an employee is a blood stream of any business. The accomplishment or disaster of the firm depends on its employee performance. Paper aimed at studying the effect of training on employee performance and to provide suggestion as to how firm can improve its employee performance through effective training programs. The study in hand faces the limitations as there are no adequate indications to correlate directly the relationship between training and employee performance.

Bandura, A. and Robert W. (1989) examined that the results show that it is possible for goal setting alone to enhance performance without a formal-knowledge-of-results program, and thus yield external validity for Locke's theory of goal setting. However, when evaluative and non evaluative feedback was added to a goal-setting program, performance was generally enhanced beyond that found in the goal-setting only group. **Bommer, W. H. et al. (2006)** suggested that objective and subjective measures of the same construct at the same level may

be used interchangeably. The analysis, however, was based on a very limited sample. Future research should address the appropriate dimensionality of employee performance. **Sturman, M. C. et al. (2005)** revealed that correlations between performance measures decreased as the time interval between performances measurements increased, but the estimates approached values greater than zero. **London, M. et al. (2004)** examined the gaps between research and practice in the areas of rater accuracy and goal setting. Prior research has shown that human resource managers may incorrectly believe that training raters to recognize errors will increase rater accuracy and that employee participation in goal setting is more effective than assigning goals. Theory-based research suggests ways to help raters recognize expected performance and enable employees to self-regulate their pursuit of goals.

Viswesvaran, C. and Deniz S. O. (2000) found that implications for human resource management in general, and performance appraisal for selection and assessment in particular, are explored. It is pointed out that the different dimensions or facets of individual job performance hypothesized in the literature are positively correlated. This positive manifold suggests the presence of a general factor which represents a common variance shared across all the dimensions or facets. **Uddin, M. J. et al. (2013)** examined the impact of organizational culture on employee performance and productivity from the perspectives of multinational companies operating especially under the telecommunication sector of Bangladesh in South Asia. They applied qualitative methodology focusing on a case study of Grameenphone (GP) (a subsidiary of Teleron in Norway), the leading telecommunication based subsidiary in Bangladesh. The paper argues that organizational culture significantly influences employee performance and productivity in the dynamic emerging context. **Patterson, M. et al. (2004)** supported in hierarchical multiple regressions for separate aspects of climate. In addition, an overall analysis showed that company productivity was more strongly correlated with those aspects of climate that had stronger satisfaction loadings. A second prediction, that managers' perceptions of climate would be more closely linked to company productivity than would those of non-managers, was not supported. However, managers' assessments of most aspects of their company's climate were significantly more positive than those of non-managers. **Gielen, A. C. et al. (2010)** used information from a panel of Dutch firms to investigate the labor productivity effects of performance related pay (PRP). We find that PRP increases productivity at the firm level with 9% and employment growth with 5%.

Belorgey, N. et al. (2006) found that the employment rate and productivity exhibit a significant negative relationship, arising from the concentration of employment on the most productive members of the workforce. Indicators of financial depth and price stability are found to be significant **Chandrasekar, K. (2011)** analyzed that the workplace environment impacts employee morale, productivity and engagement - both positively and negatively. The work place environment in a majority of industry is unsafe and unhealthy. These includes poorly designed workstations, unsuitable furniture, lack of ventilation, inappropriate lighting, excessive noise, insufficient safety measures in fire emergencies and lack of personal protective equipment. People working in such environment are prone to occupational disease and it impacts on employee's performance. Thus productivity is decreased due to the workplace environment. The analysis of the working environment at different public sector

organizations and the research done to understand the performance level of the employees due to the work environment, and also aims at suggesting few interactions to provide better work environment at Public Sector Organizations. **Manolopoulos, D. (2007)** showed that the public sector in Greece is more likely to provide extrinsic than intrinsic rewards, however the latter seems to be related to better organizational outcomes. Both individuals' ability and demographic characteristics are core determinants of employees' motivational preferences. The core of this paper tests empirically the relationship between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation with performance in a country of EU "periphery". Caution should be exercised in generalizing the results for more advanced economies. **Olivero, G. K. et al. (1997)** illustrated that training increased productivity by 22.4 percent. The coaching, which included: goal setting, collaborative problem solving, practice, feedback, supervisory involvement, evaluation of end-results, and a public presentation, increased productivity by 88.0 percent, a significantly greater gain compared to training alone. Descriptions of procedures, explanations for the results obtained, and suggestions for future research and practice are offered.

Turkyilmaz, A. et al. (2011) developed a model by including effecting factors of employee satisfaction, their relations and effects of employee satisfaction on employee loyalty. Partial least squares structural equation model was employed to test the model in the public. Data analysis reveals that there is a strong relationship between ESL in a branch of a public sector Social Security Institution in Turkey. Training and personal development was found the most effecting factor of customer satisfaction. The study also finds a positive relationship between working conditions and satisfaction. Human resource management (HRM) applications such as measuring employee satisfaction, performance development are widely used in private sector. Specifically, in developing countries such as Turkey, these applications are rarely used in the public sector. Therefore, the paper advocates the use of HRM applications in the public sector in a developing country. **Kuvaas, B. (2008)** suggested that the relationships between job autonomy and work performance and task interdependence and work performance are partly mediated by intrinsic motivation, while the relationship between supervisor support for autonomy, competence, and development and work performance is fully mediated by intrinsic motivation. Research limitations/implications – the two most important limitations, which are discussed in more detail at the end of the paper, are the cross-sectional nature of the study and the reliance on self-reported questionnaire data. The results support self-determination theory and suggest that public and private sector managers should pay more attention to autonomy-supportive work environments. Originality/value – First, a recent review of self-determination theory casts doubt on the performance implications of intrinsic motivation for less complex or interesting tasks. Thus, in order to increase our knowledge of the quality of self-determination theory as a work motivation theory, empirical research that spans a broad cross-section of jobs and functions in organizations is needed. Second, and despite the importance of motivation among public employees in an era of transformation to a more business-oriented approach, there is little empirical research on public sector employee motivation.

Ojo, O. and Dupe A. A. (2014) investigated the impact of conflict management on employees' performance in a public sector organization, a case of Power Holding Company of Nigeria (PHCN). This study adopted the survey research design. A total of 100 respondents were selected for the study using stratified sampling technique. Questionnaire was used to collect primary data. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Hypotheses were tested through regression analysis and correlation coefficient. The findings revealed that effective conflict management enhance employee's performance in an organization and that organization's conflict management system influences employee performance in the organization. It was recommended that organization should embark on training and retraining of its employees in area of conflict management so as to create a conducive working environment for the employees and that there should be efficient and effective communication between and among all categories of the employees the organization. **Rahman, M. H. (2013)** claimed that motivation remains a key secret of managing people at organizational interfaces. Different people from different background come together within organization having different aims incompatible to organizational aims. Motivation acts as key forces to drive diversified workforce to meet organizational objectives. Employees of private commercial bank scored slightly higher in both the construct however there is no significant differences have been proved about benefit received from the job and perception about job nature and environment. Differences were found between the two groups on the relative perception they placed on existing factors of motivation.

Linna, P. (2010) constructed that there was a certain mismatch between perceptions concerning productivity and the potential that lies in this concept as a functional tool in the public sector's development efforts. Public sector productivity cannot be developed and discussed without taking into consideration the issue of effectiveness. **Madden, G. et al. (1997)** compared the initial and subsequent performance of economics departments. The analysis applies survey data to a non-parametric DEA model. Model results suggest that overall performance has improved, while the gap between the performance of established and new universities has narrowed. **Handoussa, H. et al. (1986)** recommended that an important asymmetry in the consequences of the reforms between the rapidly expanding import substitution sector with high productivity growth and the stagnant traditional export sector. Our results also indicate that much of the observed productivity growth of the import substitution sector may be ascribed to improvements in capacity utilization, and suggests that Egypt's industrial policies be reassessed since such a path may not be sustainable. **Boyle, R. (2006)** focused on three main aspects of productivity measurement: attempts to develop comparative, cross-national assessments of public sector efficiency and performance; national and sectoral public sector productivity measurement initiatives; and a more micro-level examination of productivity measurement, looking at organisation-based and bottom up initiatives to measure public sector productivity.

Nyhan, R. C. (2000) proposed that participation in decision making, feedback from and to employees, and empowerment of employees lead to increased interpersonal trust (between supervisor and employee) in a public organization. The article further hypothesizes that these trust-building practices between supervisors and workers can lead to increased productivity and strengthened organizational commitment. The conceptual model is empirically tested using as a case study both structural equation modeling and data from a municipal government. The analysis demonstrates that the trust-based model is a viable paradigm for increasing interpersonal trust, organizational commitment, and productivity in the public

sector. **Buelens, M. and Herman V. d. B. (2007)** showed that public sector employees are less extrinsically motivated. Differences in hierarchical level are more important determinants of work motivation than sectoral differences. In addition, most observed differences can be wholly or partially explained by differences in job content, not by the sector itself. Evidence is presented to show that motivational differences can be explained by a positive choice of work – life balance.

Wright, B. E. (2001) found relatively little attention in the public sector; the research that does exist has been largely data driven, guided at best by theories that have not incorporated more contemporary research. **Delfgaauw, J. and Robert D. (2007)** proved that an economy in which workers differ in laziness and in public service motivation, and characterise optimal incentive contracts for public sector workers under different informational assumptions. When civil servants' effort is unverifiable, lazy workers and working in the public sector highly attractive and may crowd out dedicated workers. When effort is verifiable, the government optimally attracts dedicated workers as well as the economy's laziest workers by ordering separating contracts, which are both distorted. **Naff, K. C. and John C. (1999)** asked whether public sector employees have different values and respond to different incentives than private sector employees. the relationship between public service motivation and federal employees' attitudes and behavior by examining responses of nearly 10, 000 federal employees to a recent survey Even though the survey only contained a subset of Perry's scale, we found significant relationships between public service motivation and federal employees' job satisfaction, performance, intention to remain with the government, and support for the government's reinvention efforts. **Wright, B. E. (2007)** suggested that goal theory provides a strong theoretical foundation for understanding the independent contributions of task, mission, and public service to employee work motivation and performance. The importance of an organization's mission increases employee work motivation in the public sector by making the job more important, even after controlling for the effect of performance-related extrinsic rewards. **Georgellis, Y. et al. (2010)** investigated whether intrinsic motivation affects the sorting of employees between the private and the public sectors, paying particular attention to whether extrinsic rewards crowd out intrinsic motivation. Using British longitudinal data, we find that individuals are attracted to the public sector by the intrinsic rather than the extrinsic rewards that the sector offers. We also find evidence supporting the intrinsic motivation crowding out hypothesis, in that, higher extrinsic rewards reduce the propensity of intrinsically motivated individuals to accept public sector employment. Although our findings inform the literature on public service motivation, they also pose the question whether lower extrinsic rewards could increase the average quality of job matches in the public sector, thus improving performance without the need for high-powered incentives.

Anderfuhren, B. S. et al. (2010) explained that material incentives such as performance-related pay, and team relations and support such as recognition by superiors. Results of a Structural Equations Model clearly show the relevance of PSM. They also provide evidence for the importance of socio-relational motivating factors, whereas material incentives play an anecdotal role, suggesting the potential crowding-out of intrinsic motivation. **Weibel, A. et al. (2009)** analyzed whether the impact of pay for performance on performance is bound to conditions, and if this is the case, under which conditions pay for performance has a positive or a negative effect on performance. We explore this contingency in a meta-analytic review of previous experimental studies on the effects of pay for performance on performance. We further show why pay for performance sometimes negatively affects personal efforts. With an experimental vignette study we demonstrate (a) that motivation is likely to be a key influence on the effect of performance-related pay on performance, and (b) that pay for performance is

generally more costly as it appears because it almost always produces hidden costs of rewards. Our findings help to explain the modest success of pay for performance in the public sector. **Belorgey, N. et al. (2006)** studied productivity per employee: the determinants of its growth rate in the 1990s are first examined, and then the determinants of its level, using a more structural approach. The employment rate and productivity exhibit a significant negative relationship, arising from the concentration of employment on the most productive members of the workforce. Indicators of financial depth and price stability are found to be significant. **Langbein, L. I. (2000)** used a sample of professional engineers employed in the public and private sector to investigate the effect of sector employment, indicators of task complexity, organization size, number of rules, importance, and attentiveness and agreement among various principals (customers or clients, peers, mid- and top level management, and politicians) on both employee discretion and a subjective measure of employee productivity. The results show that disagreement among important and attentive proximate principals (mid-level managers) expands discretion, but disagreement among important and attentive distant principals (top executives and politicians) reduces discretion. Sector has no direct or indirect effect on discretion. Monitoring by mid-level management has no effect on productivity. Because disagreement among distant principals is greater in the public sector, devolution of authority alone is unlikely to increase public sector productivity. **Samuel, M. O. and Crispen C. (2009)** identified and established the key intrinsic and extrinsic motivational variables being used by selected public and private sector organizations in retaining their employees; determine the extent to which the identified intrinsic and extrinsic motivational variables are influencing employees' retention and turnover in the selected organizations; and make recommendations to management of the selected organizations on how to effectively retain employees and reduce turnover. The study adopted the cross-sectional survey research design, investigating the extent to which selected motivational variables influence employees' decision to either remain or quit an organization. Quantitative research design was used and this design was chosen because its findings are generalized and the data objective. The study examined two public and two private sector organizations. The total population of the research comprised 1800 employees of the surveyed organizations with a sample size of 145 respondents. A self-developed questionnaire, measured on a Likert Scale was used to collect data from respondents. The questionnaire had a Cronbach alpha coefficient of $\alpha = 0.85$ suggesting that the instrument was reliable. The Chi-square test of association was used in testing the hypothesis of the study. The result showed that employees in both public and private sector organizations were, to a very large extent, influenced to stay in their respective organizations by a combination of intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors. The following motivational variables were found to have significantly influenced employee retention in both the public and private sector organizations: training and development, challenging/interesting work, freedom for innovative thinking, and job security.

Chapter: 3

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

3.0 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

In this part of the study independent variables (Education, Training and Development, Physical and Psychological Strength, Compensation and Motivation, Working Environment) will be linked with dependent variables (Productivity, Financial Performance) for organizational growth.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework (Independent variables and dependent variables)

In the above figure employee's education is considered as a vital element to be achieved organizational growth. On the other hand, consistent training and development of the employee can lead organizational financial progress. Physical fitness and psychological strength of employees can bring high level of involvement on the job and increase productivity of the organizations both in public and private organizations. Employees always feel happier when they have been financially compensated along with non-financial motivation. Working environment has been considered to key factor that can lead human resources work actively and efficiently to achieve organizational goals. Therefore, above mentioned five independent factors or variables initially are considered to impact on dependent variables of organizational growth (i.e. productivity and financial performance).

3.1 Problem Statement

While conducting this research main problematic area may be considered insufficient secondary data since a few number of researches have been conducted by the researchers in the past on comparative study on public and private sectors employees, especially in Bangladesh. Besides, it is too difficult for the researchers to collect data from different government departments as they do not have direct access as per research requirements. For

conducting this study it seems that there is a little opportunity or scope to conduct research of this kind or field as human resources contribution to organizational growth through productivity and financial performance.

3.2 Rationale of the Study

As it has already been mentioned, there is no mentionable research works conducted yet in the area of measuring impact of public and private sector employees' contribution as comparative studies for the growth of organizational growth. We felt it as an ideal field to explore something of creative nature if an exhaustive research can be conducted in this area. In fact no entity such as university, research organizations or government agencies has taken pain in showing any interest to carry out such an economic study. So the main interest to work in this area has been emanated from the urge to do a basic work through carrying out a study to observe, analyze and find out impact, if any, of human resources both in public and private sectors. We believe this kind of study will be useful for further research work as well as making policy makers interested in taking new policies for the organizational productivity and financial growth which may be leading to sustainable economic development in the days ahead in Bangladesh.

3.3 Objectives of the Study

Every research should have some specific objectives. This section of the study will provide specific purposes to analyze and find out the impact of human resources on productivity and financial performance for organizational growth, taking into considerations a number of public and private organizations. As Bangladesh graduated from the developing country to the lower middle income country a couple of years back and she is in the process of graduating from being the aid-dependent economy into a self-reliant economy, the main focus of this paper is to reveal the significance of human resources in boosting national economic growth. As only private sector employees are not sufficient to generate required productivity in the economy, demands for public sectors employees have become obvious. The paper will analyze the trends of both public and private sectors employees on productivity and financial performance for organizational growth in Bangladesh.

To some extent the specific objectives of the study will be as follows:

- i) To present the status of human resources in public and private sectors in Bangladesh and trend of organizational growth;
- ii) To outline the major policies attracting human resources in Bangladesh;
- iii) To analyze financial performance of employees some of government and non government organizations in Bangladesh
- iv) To identify major problems of human resources in Bangladesh; and
- v) To provide some modest suggestions to develop human resources for government and non-government organizations in Bangladesh to increase organizational growth rapidly.

3.4 Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant impact of education of employees on financial growth of government and private organizations in Bangladesh.

H₀₂: There is no significant impact of training and development of employees on financial growth of government and private organizations in Bangladesh.

H₀₃: There is no significant impact of physical and psychological Strength of employees on financial growth of government and private organizations in Bangladesh.

H₀₄: There is no significant impact of compensation and motivation of employees on financial growth of government and private organizations in Bangladesh.

H₀₅: There is no significant impact of working environment of employees on financial growth of government and private organizations in Bangladesh.

Chapter: 4
METHODOLOGY

4.0 METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

4.1 Area of the Study

This study has been confined to find out the impact of human resources on productivity and financial performance for organizational growth of Bangladesh. The research has been selected as per their direct contribution in the economic growth of Bangladesh.

4.2 Research Design

Both quantitative and qualitative research methods have been adapted to collect secondary data. For conducting the survey report has been administered through related public and private organizations and journals, articles and other websites.

4.3 Population of the Study

The target population for this research has been considered for both public and private sector employees. In this study, the accessible population has been comprised of all the above mentioned stakeholders of human resources of Bangladesh.

4.4 Sampling of the Study

Stratified random sampling technique has been adopted in this research. The researchers decided what needed to be known and set out to find employees who were willing to provide the information by virtue of knowledge or experience. Therefore, accessible population was divided into different strata or batch to draw the random sample. In the sample more than five years experienced employees were given preference to be a sample for the study.

4.5 Sample Size of the Study

For some studies, the population may be small enough to warrant the inclusion of all of them in the study. But a study may entail a large population which cannot all be studied. That portion of the population that is studied is called a sample of the population. A sample in this study is, therefore, a smaller group of elements drawn through a definite procedure from an accessible population. In this study, there were mainly 190 employees (public sectors 80, private sectors 80) considered as sample size.

4.6 Data Collection Tools and Techniques

To investigate impact of the impact of human resources on productivity and financial performance for organizational growth in Bangladesh researches questions were answered using different tools and techniques. In addition, both qualitative and quantitative data were collected from secondary sources like books, journal articles, newspapers and other sources along with primary data through self-administrated structured questioner. The researcher designed an interview schedule as one of the data collection instrument for this study using both structured and unstructured interview guidelines.

4.7 Method of Data Collection

After the pilot testing and all necessary modifications, the researchers went directly to the related departments to collect different articles, documents for the study in the selected areas.

4.8 Method of data Analysis

The collected data from both primary and secondary sources were observed, analyzed through the simple statistical tools i.e. discrete statistics, multiple regression analysis, time series analysis and other necessary methods using SPSS and Microsoft Office Excel software tools.

4.9 Method of Data Presentation

By analyzing the data results were presented in the form of tables, pie charts, percentage and other logical ways as per requirements.

Chapter: 5

DATA ANALYSES & FINDINGS

5.0 DATA ANALYSES AND FINDINGS

In this section of the research numerous analyses have been done such as; descriptive statistics, reliability test, multiple regression analysis, time series analysis to reach the objective of the research.

5.1 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics generally shows proper description of data set which has been previously surveyed by the researchers. In this study, total 180 (90 from public organizations and 90 from private organizations) valid samples were considered to analyze and interpret their responses through specific methods of analyses as per achieving objective of the research. All descriptive statistics have been shown by frequency tables, pie chart etc.

Frequencies

		Statistics			
		Gender	Age	Education	Profession
N	Valid	180	180	180	180
	Missing	0	0	0	0
Range		1.00	3.00	3.00	1.00
Minimum		1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Maximum		2.00	4.00	4.00	2.00

Table 1: Frequency Statistics
Source: Microsoft office Excel Data Output

In the table 1, shows that all frequencies relating to the gender, age, education, profession of the samples were valid 100%, there was no missing frequencies at all. Table 1 also shows range value of the gender, age, education, profession of the samples along with minimum and maximum values of the survey questionnaire.

Frequency Table and Pie Chart Analysis

		Gender			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	117	65.0	65.0	65.0
	Female	63	35.0	35.0	100.0
Total		180	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Frequency Statistics on Gender
Source: Microsoft office Excel Data Output

Chart 1: Statistics on Gender
Source: Microsoft office Excel Data Output

Table 2 and pie chart 1, indicates to individual characteristics of the samples i.e. among the sample size of 180 there were 117 samples or 65% male employees. Conversely, there were 63 samples or 35% female employees. These results suggest that still in Bangladesh rate of women in the workforce is not up to the mark but present government trying to equalize it rapidly.

		Age			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Below 25	15	8.3	8.3	8.3
	25-35	67	37.2	37.2	45.6
	35-45	85	47.2	47.2	92.8
	45 Above	13	7.2	7.2	100.0
Total		180	100.0	100.0	

Table 3: Frequency Statistics on Age
Source: Microsoft office Excel Data Output

Chart 2: Statistics on Age
Source: Microsoft office Excel Data Output

Table 3 and pie chart 2, shows that the age range of the surveyed 15 samples or 8.3% was below 25 years of age, 67 samples or 37.2% was 25 to 35 years old, 85 samples or 47.2% was 35 to 45 years of age and 13 samples or 7.2% was 45 and above years of age of the observed employees. These suggest that in Bangladesh energetic, capable employees' rate is very high

that can bring organizational growth and economic growth as well as their age range between 25 to 45 years respectively. Therefore, impressive opportunities may have for the economy if human resources are properly utilized.

		Education			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Undergraduate	13	7.2	7.2	7.2
	Graduate	67	37.2	37.2	44.4
	Post Graduate	93	51.7	51.7	96.1
	Doctorate	7	3.9	3.9	100.0
Total		180	100.0	100.0	

Table 4: Frequency Statistics on Education
Source: Microsoft office Excel Data Output

Chart 3: Statistics on Education
Source: Microsoft office Excel Data Output

The education have been found in the samples that 13 samples or 7.2% was undergraduates, 67 samples or 37.2% was graduates, 93 samples or 51.7% was post graduates and 7 samples or 3.9% was above post graduates of the observed samples. Table 4 and pie chart 3, suggests that maximum 51.7% employees have done their post graduates that should be increased by country in future to get high contribute specialized human resources in accomplishment of specialized tasks. Organizations should also try to seek for educated employees in term of the higher degree as per requirement.

		Profession			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Public Job	90	50.0	50.0	50.0
	Private Job	90	50.0	50.0	100.0
Total		180	100.0	100.0	

Table 5: Frequency Statistics on Profession
Source: Microsoft office Excel Data Output

Chart 4: Statistics on Profession
Source: Microsoft office Excel Data Output

In the table 5 and pie chart 4 suggests that 90 or 50% samples has been drawn from selected public organizations and 90 or 50% samples has been drawn from selected private organizations to conduct this research.

5.2 Equity and Net Profit Analysis for five years

In this part of the study equity and net profit have been studied considering latest consecutive five years financial statements of both public and private organizations to know the financial performances that might be contributed by the organizational employees.

5.2.1 Selected Public Organizations: PETROBANGLA

Chart - 5 represents the equity and net profit banalyses for the five years 2014 to 2018 of PETROBANGLA. In the following chart - 5, red color indicates stockholders' equity (Tk. in million) and blue color specifies net profit after tax. On the other hand 'Y' axis represents both stcok holders equity & net profit after tax and 'X' axis represents financial years respectively.

Chart 5: Equity and Net Profit of PETROBANGLA
Source: Microsoft office Excel Data Output

Chart-5, identifies that financial year 2013-14 was the highest net profit after tax about BDT. 2,50,000 million with highest value of stockholders equity near BDT. 50,000 million. But gradually both profit and equity level were declining specially 2014-15 to 2015-16 financial years. Conversely, net profit in the financial years respectively 2016-2017 to 2017-2018 was negative with lower value of stockholders equity of PETROBANGLA. The results suggest that financial performance of PETROBANGLA was downward over the years. It can be evidence that there is wide scope to improve the contributions of the employees of PETROBANGLA.

TITAS GAS

Chart - 6 represents the equity and net profit analyses for the five years 2014 to 2018 of TITAS GAS. In the following chart - 6, red color indicates stockholders' equity (Tk. in million) and blue color specifies net profit after tax. On the other hand 'Y' axis represents both stockholders equity & net profit after tax and 'X' axis represents financial years respectively.

Chart 6: Equity and Net Profit of TITAS GAS
Source: Microsoft office Excel Data Output

In the above chart recognizes that FY 2014-15 was the highest net profit after tax almost BDT. 10,000 million and highest value of stockholders equity was in the FY 2017-18 about BDT. 61,000 million. Though stockholders' equity was improving, net profit was decreasing over the years. It means that there was some issues regarding reduction of profit gradually of Titas Gas. According to analyses this organization was trying to increase its assets rather improving its employees performances to earn consistent and higher level of profit from the operations.

DESCO

Chart - 7 represents the equity and net profit analyses for the five years 2014 to 2018 of DESCO. In the following chart - 7, red color indicates stockholders' equity (Tk. in million)

and blue color specifies net profit after tax. On the other hand ‘Y’ axis represents both stock holders equity & net profit after tax and ‘X’ axis represents financial years respectively.

Chart 7: Equity and Net Profit of DESCO
Source: Microsoft office Excel Data Output

Chart-7, prescribes that FY 201-16 was the highest net profit after tax about BDT. 1,500 million. On the other hand, highest value of stockholders equity was in the FY 2017-18 about BDT. 3,000 million. There was ups and downs in profits as well as equity over the years of DESCO. This results suggests that inconsistent financial performances have been experienced by the organization during the periods.

5.2.2 Selected Private Organizations: ACI

Chart - 8 represents the equity and net profit analyses for the five years 2014 to 2018 of ACI. In the following chart - 8, red color indicates stockholders' equity (Tk. in million) and blue color specifies net profit after tax. On the other hand ‘Y’ axis represents both stock holders equity & net profit after tax and ‘X’ axis represents financial years respectively.

Chart 8: Equity and Net Profit of ACI Group
 Source: Microsoft office Excel Data Output

In the above chart-8, represents that stockholders' equity was improving over the years though slightly fluctuations were there in the net profits. ACI was trying to increase its equity over the periods to have sustainability in the long run.

BEXIMCO

Chart - 9 represents the equity and net profit banalyses for the five years 2014 to 2018 of ACI. In the following chart - 9, red color indicates stockholders' equity (Tk. in million) and blue color specifies net profit after tax. On the other hand 'Y' axis represents both stcok holders equity & net profit after tax and 'X' axis represents financial years respectively.

Chart 9: Equity and Net Profit of BEXIMCO Group
 Source: Microsoft office Excel Data Output

Chart-9 entails that stockholders' equity was upward sloppy over the observed periods. Net profit was also consistent although maximum portion of the profit was utilized to increase equity of the stockholders.

SQUARE

Chart - 10 represents the equity and net profit banalyses for the five years 2014 to 2018 of ACI. In the following chart - 10, red color indicates stockholders' equity (Tk. in million) and blue color specifies net profit after tax. On the other hand 'Y' axis represents both stcok holders equity & net profit after tax and 'X' axis represents financial years respectively.

Chart 10: Equity and Net Profit of SQUARE Group
Source: Microsoft office Excel Data Output

In the chart-10 shows that SQUARE had been performing well over the observed periods as it had consistent financial performances in terms of net profit and stockholders equity.

5.3 Data Reliability Test

Case Processing Summary			
		N	%
Cases	Valid	180	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	180	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.985	6

Table 6: Data Reliability Test Summary
Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

The question of reliability rises as the function of scales is stretched to encompass the realm of prediction. One of the most reliability statistics in use today is Cronbach's alpha - Santos, J. R. A. (1999). Cronbach's alpha is the convenient test used to estimate reliability or internal consistency of a composite score. Usually it gives a result 0 to 1 but sometimes negative results may provide. Negative result indicates data in not fit for the test. On the other hand, general rule of thumb, Cronbach's alpha .70 and above is the good result, .80 and above better result and .90 and above is the best. Therefore, in the Table 1, Cronbach's alpha for the thirty items is almost .99 or 99%, suggesting that the items has the best internal consistency of the independent variables (education, training and development, physical and

psychological strength, compensation and motivation, working environment) on dependent variable of organizational growth of private and government organizations.

5.4 Regression Analysis

Statistical data analysis programs commonly compute the p-values during the execution of hypothesis test. Adjusted R-squared, on the other hand, gives the percentage of variation explained by only those independent variables that in reality affect the dependent variable.

5.4.1 Education on organizational growth (H₀₁)

A regression equation was run through SPSS to find out whether independent variable (education, a human skill factor) had significant impact on dependent variable (organizational growth). Null hypothesis (H₀₁) was stated that there was no significant impact of independent variable on dependent variable. In the tables 4, 5: $b = .93$, $t(178) = 2.92$ and $p < .05$, on the other hand, results shown by calculations in the tables 3, 4: $F(1, 178) = 1136.490$, $p < .001$, with an adjusted $R^2 = .86$. The regression equation is; $Y = a + bX$ (where, Y = dependent variable, b = slope, X = independent variable and a = constant). Therefore, the equation was found as, $Y = .35 + .93X$. The regression model states that if p value (probability value) is lesser than alpha value (standard level of significance, $\alpha = .05$) then the model is significant. In this study, developed model was highly significant with p value ($p < .001$) at the standard level of significance level ($\alpha = .05$). On the other hand, adjusted R^2 (adjusted R^2 indicates that the percentage of variation explained by only the independent variables that actually affect the dependent variable) .86 or 86% of variance in dependent variable (organizational growth) which could be explained by independent variable (education). Precisely, it was found that there was significant impact on independent variable (education, a human skill variable) on dependent variable (organizational growth) for the government and non government organizations. Therefore, null hypothesis was rejected. Finally, it is concluded that employees' education has significant impact on organizational growth.

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Education ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Growth

b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.930 ^a	.865	.864	.254

a. Predictors: (Constant), Education

Table 7: Regression Model Summary

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	73.101	1	73.101	1136.490	.000 ^b
Residual	11.449	178	.064		
Total	84.550	179			

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Growth

b. Predictors: (Constant), Education

Table 8: ANOVA Model Summary

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.354	.121		2.923	.004
Education	.922	.027	.930	33.712	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Growth

Table 9: Regression Coefficients Model Summary

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

5.4.2 Training and development on organizational growth (H₀₂)

A regression equation was run through SPSS to find out whether independent variable (training and development, a human skill factor) had significant impact on dependent variable (organizational growth). Null hypothesis (H₀₂) was stated that there was no significant impact of independent variable on dependent variable. In the tables 4, 5: $b = .87$, $t(178) = 4.92$ and $p < .05$, on the other hand, results shown by calculations in the tables 3, 4: $F(1, 178) = 570.589$, $p < .001$, with an adjusted $R^2 = .76$. The regression equation is; $Y = a + bX$ (where, Y = dependent variable, b = slope, X = independent variable and a = constant). Therefore, the equation was found as, $Y = .76 + .87X$. The regression model states that if p value (probability value) is lesser than alpha value (standard level of significance, $\alpha = .05$) then the model is significant. In this study, developed model was highly significant with p value ($p < .001$) at the standard level of significance level ($\alpha = .05$). On the other hand, adjusted R^2 (adjusted R^2 indicates that the percentage of variation explained by only the independent variables that actually affect the dependent variable) .76 or 76% of variance in dependent variable (organizational growth) which could be explained by independent variable (training and development). Precisely, it was found that there was significant impact on independent variable (training and development, a human skill variable) on dependent variable (organizational growth) for the government and non government organizations. Consequently, null hypothesis was rejected. Finally, it is concluded that employees' training and development has significant impact on organizational growth.

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Training and Development ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Growth

b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.873 ^a	.762	.761	.336

a. Predictors: (Constant), Training and Development

Table 10: Regression Model Summary

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	64.446	1	64.446	570.589	.000 ^b
	Residual	20.104	178	.113		
	Total	84.550	179			

- a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Growth
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Training and Development

Table 11: ANOVA Model Summary
 Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.757	.154		4.916	.000
Training and Development	.837	.035	.873	23.887	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Growth

Table 12: Regression Coefficients Model Summary
 Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

5.4.3 Physical and psychological strength on organizational growth (H₀₃)

A regression equation was run through SPSS to find out whether independent variable (physical and psychological strength, a human physical and mental factor) had significant impact on dependent variable (organizational growth). Null hypothesis (H₀₃) was stated that there was no significant impact of independent variable on dependent variable. In the tables 4, 5: $b = .97$, $t(178) = 2.25$ and $p < .05$, on the other hand, results shown by calculations in the tables 3, 4: $F(1, 178) = 2928.804$, $p < .001$, with an adjusted $R^2 = .94$. The regression equation is; $Y = a + bX$ (where, Y = dependent variable, b = slope, X = independent variable and a = constant). Therefore, the equation was found as, $Y = .18 + .97X$. The regression model states that if p value (probability value) is lesser than alpha value (standard level of significance, $\alpha = .05$) then the model is significant. In this study, developed model was highly significant with p value ($p < .001$) at the standard level of significance level ($\alpha = .05$). On the other hand, adjusted R^2 (adjusted R^2 indicates that the percentage of variation explained by only the independent variables that actually affect the dependent variable) .97 or 97% of variance in dependent variable (organizational growth) which could be explained by independent variable (physical and psychological strength). Precisely, it was found that there was significant impact on independent variable (physical and psychological strength, a human physical and mental variable) on dependent variable (organizational growth) for the government and non government organizations. Thus, null hypothesis was rejected. Finally, it is concluded that employees' physical and psychological strength has significant impact on organizational growth.

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Physical and Psychological Strength ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Growth

b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.971 ^a	.943	.942	.165

a. Predictors: (Constant), Physical and Psychological Strength

Table 13: Regression Model Summary
 Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	79.706	1	79.706	2928.804	.000 ^b
	Residual	4.844	178	.027		
	Total	84.550	179			

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Growth

b. Predictors: (Constant), Physical and Psychological Strength

Table 14: ANOVA Model Summary

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.177	.079		2.250	.026
	Physical and Psychological Strength	.958	.018	.971	54.118	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Growth

Table 15: Regression Coefficients Model Summary

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

5.4.4 Compensation and motivation on organizational growth (H₀₄)

A regression equation was run through SPSS to find out whether independent variable (compensation and motivation, a human financial and motivational factor) had significant impact on dependent variable (organizational growth). Null hypothesis (H₀₄) was stated that there was no significant impact of independent variable on dependent variable. In the tables 4, 5: $b = .97$, $t(178) = 2.87$ and $p < .05$, on the other hand, results shown by calculations in the tables 3, 4: $F(1, 178) = 2984.712$, $p < .001$, with an adjusted $R^2 = .94$. The regression equation is; $Y = a + bX$ (where, Y = dependent variable, b = slope, X = independent variable and a = constant). Therefore, the equation was found as, $Y = .22 + .97X$. The regression model states that if p value (probability value) is lesser than alpha value (standard level of significance, $\alpha = .05$) then the model is significant. In this study, developed model was highly significant with p value ($p < .001$) at the standard level of significance level ($\alpha = .05$). On the other hand, adjusted R^2 (adjusted R^2 indicates that the percentage of variation explained by only the independent variables that actually affect the dependent variable) .97 or 97% of variance in dependent variable (organizational growth) which could be explained by independent variable (physical and psychological strength). Precisely, it was found that there was significant impact on independent variable (compensation and motivation, a human financial and motivational variable) on dependent variable (organizational growth) for the government and non government organizations. Thus, null hypothesis was rejected. Finally, it is concluded that employees' compensation and motivation has significant impact on organizational growth.

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Compensation and Motivation ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Growth

b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.971 ^a	.944	.943	.164

a. Predictors: (Constant), Compensation and Motivation

Table 16: Regression Model Summary

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	79.791	1	79.791	2984.712	.000 ^b
	Residual	4.759	178	.027		
	Total	84.550	179			

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Growth

b. Predictors: (Constant), Compensation and Motivation

Table 17: ANOVA Model Summary
Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.221	.077		2.859	.005
	Compensation and Motivation	.953	.017	.971	54.633	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Growth

Table 18: Regression Coefficients Model Summary
Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

5.4.5 Working Environment on organizational growth (H₀₅)

A regression equation was run through SPSS to find out whether independent variable (working environment, a human required favorable working environment factor) had significant impact on dependent variable (organizational growth). Null hypothesis (H₀₅) was stated that there was no significant impact of independent variable on dependent variable. In the tables 4, 5: $b = .88$, $t(178) = 3.90$ and $p < .05$, on the other hand, results shown by calculations in the tables 3, 4: $F(1, 178) = 639.275$, $p < .001$, with an adjusted $R^2 = .78$. The regression equation is; $Y = a + bX$ (where, Y = dependent variable, b = slope, X = independent variable and a = constant). Therefore, the equation was found as, $Y = .59 + .88X$. The regression model states that if p value (probability value) is lesser than alpha value (standard level of significance, $\alpha = .05$) then the model is significant. In this study, developed model was highly significant with p value ($p < .001$) at the standard level of significance level ($\alpha = .05$). On the other hand, adjusted R^2 (adjusted R^2 indicates that the percentage of variation explained by only the independent variables that actually affect the dependent variable) .88 or 88% of variance in dependent variable (organizational growth) which could be explained by independent variable (working environment). In particular, it was found that there was significant impact on independent variable (working environment, a human required favorable working environment variable) on dependent variable (organizational growth) for the government and non government organizations. Hence, null hypothesis was rejected. Finally, it is concluded that employees' working environment has significant impact on organizational growth.

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Working Environment ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Growth

b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.884 ^a	.782	.781	.322

a. Predictors: (Constant), Working Environment

Table 19: Regression Model Summary

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	66.135	1	66.135	639.275	.000 ^b
	Residual	18.415	178	.103		
	Total	84.550	179			

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Growth

b. Predictors: (Constant), Working Environment

Table 20: ANOVA Model Summary

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.592	.152		3.902	.000
	Working Environment	.869	.034	.884	25.284	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Growth

Table 21: Regression Coefficients Model Summary

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

5.5 Time Series Analysis

In this part of the study time series analysis has been adopted using SPSS to find out more insight of financial performances and trends of public and private sector organizations. Five consecutive financial statements have been considered to run time series analysis.

5.5.1 Government Organizations: PETROBANGLA

Model Description	
Model Name	MOD_7
Series or Sequence	1 net_profit_petrobangla_tk_million
Transformation	None
Non-Seasonal Differencing	0
Seasonal Differencing	0
Length of Seasonal Period	No periodicity
Horizontal Axis Labels	Date_
Intervention Onsets	None
Reference Lines	None
Area Below the Curve	Not filled

Applying the model specifications from MOD_7

Case Processing Summary

		net_profit_petrobangla_tk_million
Series or Sequence Length		5
Number of Missing Values in the Plot	User-Missing System-Missing	0 0

Figure 2: Net profit Trend of PETROBANGLA during FY 2013-14 to 2017-18
Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

In the figure 2, net profit (Tk. in million) of Petrobangla has been shown for the FY 2013-14 to 2017-18. The figure shows that FY 2013-14 Petrobangla has net profit Tk. 40,000 million (forty thousand million) but gradually it lost its profitability. Consequently, from the FY 2014-15 to 2017-18 FY it has been carrying negative profitability. It seems to be very insignificant and poor financial performances over the years for its shareholders and also for the economy. Though financial statements very often shows that a big amount of profit has been utilizing for the development of organization as a result it becomes losing organization. On the other hand, government has been consistently subsidizing the organization over the periods to run it smoothly.

Equity Analysis of Petrobangla

Model Description		
Model Name		MOD_8
Series or Sequence	1	shareholders_equity_petrobangla_tk_million
Transformation		None
Non-Seasonal Differencing		0
Seasonal Differencing		0
Length of Seasonal Period		No periodicity
Horizontal Axis Labels		Date_
Intervention Onsets		None
Reference Lines		None
Area Below the Curve		Not filled

Applying the model specifications from MOD_8

Case Processing Summary

		shareholders_equity_petrobangla_tk_million
Series or Sequence Length		5
Number of Missing Values in the Plot	User-Missing	0
	System-Missing	0

Figure 3: Change in Equity of PETROBANGLA during FY 2013-14 to 2017-18
Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

Like in the figure 2, equity (Tk. in million) of Petrobangla also has been seen as declining trend in the observed years. The figure 3 has been shown the equity of shareholders for the FY 2013-14 to 2017-18. It shows that FY 2013-14 Petrobangla has equity Tk. 2,50,000 million (two lac fifty million) but in the FY 2014-15 it came down to Tk. 1,00,000 (one lac million). It has been found in the figure that FY 2014-15 to 2017-18 has not been reached at desired level in term of equity of the organization.

Profit Analysis of Titas Gas

Model Description	
Model Name	MOD_9
Series or Sequence	1
Transformation	net_profit_titas_tk_million
Non-Seasonal Differencing	None
Seasonal Differencing	0
Length of Seasonal Period	0
Horizontal Axis Labels	No periodicity
Intervention Onsets	Date_
Reference Lines	None
Area Below the Curve	None
	Not filled

Applying the model specifications from MOD_9

Case Processing Summary

		net_profit_titas_tk_million
Series or Sequence Length		5
Number of Missing Values in the Plot	User-Missing	0
	System-Missing	0

Figure 4: Net profit Trend of Titas Gas during FY 2013-14 to 2017-18
Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

In the figure 4, net profit (Tk. in million) of Titas Gas has been shown for the FY 2013-14 to 2017-18. The figure shows that FY 2013-14 Titas Gas has net profit Tk. 9,000 million (nine thousand million) and it has become top in the FY 2014-15 at 10,500 million (ten thousand five hundred million) but slowly it lost its profitability. Consequently, it has been seen in the graph that FY 2017-18 it has become lowest profitability among the observed years by Tk. 5,000 million (five thousand million). Therefore it is also an organization that does not allow smiling of its shareholders.

Equity Analysis of Titas Gas

Model Description	
Model Name	MOD_10
Series or Sequence	1
	shareholders_equity_titas_tk_million
Transformation	None
Non-Seasonal Differencing	0
Seasonal Differencing	0
Length of Seasonal Period	No periodicity
Horizontal Axis Labels	Date_
Intervention Onsets	None
Reference Lines	None
Area Below the Curve	Not filled

Applying the model specifications from MOD_10

Case Processing Summary

		shareholders_equity_titas_tk_million
Series or Sequence Length		5
Number of Missing Values in the Plot	User-Missing	0
	System-Missing	0

Figure 5: Change in Equity of Titas Gas during FY 2013-14 to 2017-18
Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

The figure 5 has been shown the equity of shareholders for the FY 2013-14 to 2017-18. In the figure 5, equity (Tk. in million) of Titas Gas has been seen as upward trend surprisingly among the selected government organizations. It shows that FY 2013-14 Titas Gas has equity Tk. 45,000 million (forty five thousand million) and in the FY 2017-18 it has gone up to Tk. 65,000 (sixty five thousand million). It has been found in the figure consistent upward trend over the years.

Profit Analysis of DESCO

Model Description

Model Name	MOD_11
Series or Sequence	1
Transformation	net_profit_desco_tk_million
Non-Seasonal Differencing	None
Seasonal Differencing	0
Length of Seasonal Period	0
Horizontal Axis Labels	No periodicity
Intervention Onsets	Date_
Reference Lines	None
Area Below the Curve	None
	Not filled

Applying the model specifications from MOD_11

Case Processing Summary		net_profit_desco_tk_million
Series or Sequence Length		5
Number of Missing Values in the Plot	User-Missing	0
	System-Missing	0

Figure 6: Net profit Trend of DESCO during FY 2013-14 to 2017-18
Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

In the figure 6, net profit (Tk. in million) of DESCO has been shown for the FY 2013-14 to 2017-18. The figure shows that FY 2013-14 DESCO has net profit Tk. 800 million (eight hundred million) and in the FY 2014-15 it has become top position in term of profit by Tk 1,600 million (one thousand six hundred million). But in the the FY 2016-17 to FY 2017-18 it has been downward profitability. Therefore, the curve seems to be almost 'A' shape. It is suggesting that company's operations or other variables are not up to the mark to get a desired profit for the shareholders.

Equity Analysis of DESCO

Model Description	
Model Name	MOD_12
Series or Sequence	1
Transformation	shareholders_equity_desco_tk_million
Non-Seasonal Differencing	None
Seasonal Differencing	0
Length of Seasonal Period	0
Horizontal Axis Labels	No periodicity
Intervention Onsets	Date_
Reference Lines	None
Area Below the Curve	None
	Not filled

Applying the model specifications from MOD_12

Case Processing Summary

		shareholders_equity_desco_tk_million
Series or Sequence Length		5
Number of Missing Values in the Plot	User-Missing	0
	System-Missing	0

Figure 7: Change in Equity of DESCO during FY 2013-14 to 2017-18
Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

The figure 7, represents equity (Tk. in million) of DESCO for FY 2013-14 to 2017-18. It has some ups and downs in the equity generation. Overall it seems to be upward trend over the years. DESCO has equity in the figure Tk. 800 million (eight hundred million) in the FY 2013-14 though it has become down to Tk. 600 (six hundred million) in the FY 2014-15. On the other hand, FY 2017-18 is shown in the figure that its profitability is going well.

Profit and Equity Forecasting of Petrobangla, Titas and DESCO for 2018-22

Model Description			Model Type
Model ID	net_profit_petrobangla_tk_million	Model_1	Holt
	shareholders_equity_petrobangla_tk_million	Model_2	ARIMA(0,0,0)
	net_profit_titas_tk_million	Model_3	Holt
	shareholders_equity_titas_tk_million	Model_4	Brown
	net_profit_desco_tk_million	Model_5	ARIMA(0,0,0)
	shareholders_equity_desco_tk_million	Model_6	Holt

Model Summary

Model Fit

Fit Statistic	Mean	SE	Minimum	Maximum	Percentile						
					5	10	25	50	75	90	95
Stationary R-squared	.338	.535	-.365	.916	-.365	-.365	-.091	.285	.907	.916	.916
R-squared	.555	.437	-2.220E-16	.958	-2.220E-16	-2.220E-16	1.360E-15	.747	.897	.958	.958
RMSE	14350.511	26997.102	445.561	68408.018	445.561	445.561	524.679	1349.377	27601.765	68408.018	68408.018
MAPE	148.376	282.705	1.669	721.751	1.669	1.669	8.142	31.818	250.112	721.751	721.751
MaxAPE	642.269	1347.381	3.677	3382.170	3.677	3.677	17.243	61.013	1088.525	3382.170	3382.170
MAE	9998.373	19207.399	275.608	48606.703	275.608	275.608	353.182	893.101	18858.690	48606.703	48606.703
MaxAE	24439.554	48149.849	485.696	121516.758	485.696	485.696	788.024	1857.246	45402.872	121516.758	121516.758
Normalized BIC	16.314	3.964	12.842	22.588	12.842	12.842	12.920	14.884	20.450	22.588	22.588

Table 22: Time Series Modeler Composite Statistics for Petrobangla, Titas Gas and DESCO
Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

In the table 22, Time Series Modeler Composite Statistics for Petrobangla, Titas Gas and DESCO has been presented. Overall statistics of all the organizations for financial forecasting may not be satisfactory for the shareholders as there are almost poor or negative scenarios in the model statistics value like Stationary R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, MaxAPE, MAE, MaxAE, Normalized BIC etc. though there are some ups and downs in the equities of organizations. Stability is concerned; the organizations are not in good shape in terms of financial performances.

Forecast

Model		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
net_profit_petrobangla_tk_million-Model_1	Forecast	-41584.293	-55801.186	-70018.079	-84234.972	-98451.865
	UCL	2968.938	-9293.238	-21634.278	-34045.338	-46519.113
	LCL	-86137.524	-102309.134	-118401.880	-134424.606	-150384.617
shareholders_equity_petrobangla_tk_million-Model_2	Forecast	130937.161	130937.161	130937.161	130937.161	130937.161
	UCL	320868.269	320868.269	320868.269	320868.269	320868.269
	LCL	-58993.947	-58993.947	-58993.947	-58993.947	-58993.947
net_profit_titas_tk_million-Model_3	Forecast	5062.244	3958.439	2854.633	1750.828	647.023
	UCL	8860.171	7756.373	6652.585	5548.810	4445.053
	LCL	1264.317	160.504	-943.318	-2047.154	-3151.007
shareholders_equity_titas_tk_million-Model_4	Forecast	68897.018	73010.826	77124.634	81238.441	85352.249
	UCL	73076.556	82356.416	92762.697	104130.141	116347.687
	LCL	64717.480	63665.235	61486.570	58346.742	54356.812
net_profit_desco_tk_million-Model_5	Forecast	746.200	746.200	746.200	746.200	746.200
	UCL	2276.164	2276.164	2276.164	2276.164	2276.164
	LCL	-783.764	-783.764	-783.764	-783.764	-783.764
shareholders_equity_desco_tk_million-Model_6	Forecast	3770.895	4435.330	5099.765	5764.200	6428.635
	UCL	5188.868	5915.282	6639.206	7360.919	8080.650
	LCL	2352.922	2955.378	3560.324	4167.481	4776.620

For each model, forecasts start after the last non-missing in the range of the requested estimation period, and end at the last period for which non-missing values of all the predictors are available or at the end date of the requested forecast period, whichever is earlier.

Table 23: Net Profit and Equity Forecasting for 2018-22 of PETROBANGLA, Titas Gas and DESCO
Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

The table 23 represents the forecasting of net profit and equity for the FY 2018-19 to FY 2022-23 of Petrobangla, Titas Gas and DESCO. From the first two rows of the table represents Petrobangla's forecasting of net profit and equity for next five years respectively. It does not show mentionable stability of financial performances of the organization. On the other hand, performances of Titas in terms of net profit represent also inconsistent and poor which may continue over the years though its equity shows some consistency somehow. Finally, DESCO has mixed scenarios as net profits may go down most of the periods and sometimes it may up.

Figure 8: Net Profit and Equity Forecasting for 2018-22 of PETROBANGLA, Titas Gas and DESCO
Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

The figure 8 represents the forecasting of net profit and equity for the FY 2018-19 to FY 2022-23 of Petrobangla, Titas Gas and DESCO. The different curves like red color presents observed value and blue presents forecasting value of selected government organizations. From the first two portions of the figure represents Petrobangla's observed and forecasting net profit and equity for last five years and next five years respectively. In the observed curve (red) does not show any stability of the organization along with forecasting curve (blue). On the other side, Titas observed curve shows also inconsistent poor performances over the years as forecasting follows the same trend of the organization. But its equity shows some consistency somehow in both observed and forecasting curves which may bring some hope for the shareholder and stakeholders. Last but not least, DESCO has mixed scenarios as net profits goes down most of the periods and sometimes it ups inconsistently in the observed periods and forecasting curve may take place similar things in the following years. Its equity has got some resistant in terms of better future trend.

5.5.2 Private Organizations (ACI, BEXIMCO and SQUARE):

Profit Analysis of ACI

Model Description

Model Name	MOD_1
Series or Sequence	1
Transformation	net_profit_aci_tk_million
Non-Seasonal Differencing	None
Seasonal Differencing	0
Length of Seasonal Period	0
Horizontal Axis Labels	No periodicity
Intervention Onsets	Date_
Reference Lines	None
Area Below the Curve	None
	Not filled

Applying the model specifications from MOD_1

Case Processing Summary

		net_profit_aci_tk_million
Series or Sequence Length		5
Number of Missing Values in the Plot	User-Missing	0
	System-Missing	0

Figure 9: Net profit Trend of ACI during FY 2013-14 to 2017-18
Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

In the figure 9, net profit (Tk. in million) of ACI has been shown for the FY 2013-14 to 2017-18. The figure shows that FY 2013-14 ACI has net profit Tk. 40,000 million (forty thousand million) but gradually it lost its profitability. Consequently, from the FY 2014-15 to 2017-18 FY it has been carrying negative profitability. It seems to be very insignificant and poor financial performances over the years for its shareholders and also for the economy. Though financial statements very often shows that a big amount of profit has been utilizing for the

development of organization as a result it becomes loosing organization. On the other hand, government has been consistently subsidizing the organization over the periods to run it smoothly.

Equity Analysis of ACI

Model Description

Model Name	MOD_2
Series or Sequence	1
Transformation	shareholders_equity_aci_tk_million
Non-Seasonal Differencing	None
Seasonal Differencing	0
Length of Seasonal Period	0
Horizontal Axis Labels	No periodicity
Intervention Onsets	Date_
Reference Lines	None
Area Below the Curve	None
	Not filled

Applying the model specifications from MOD_2

Case Processing Summary

		shareholders_equity_aci_tk_million
Series or Sequence Length		5
Number of Missing Values in the Plot	User-Missing	0
	System-Missing	0

Figure 10: Change in Equity of ACI during FY 2013-14 to 2017-18
Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

Like in the figure 10, equity (Tk. in million) of ACI also has been seen as declining trend in the observed years. The figure 3 has been shown the equity of shareholders for the FY 2013-14 to 2017-18. It shows that FY 2013-14 ACI has equity Tk. 2,50,000 million (two lac fifty

million) but in the FY 2014-15 it came down to Tk. 1,00,000 (one lac million). It has been found in the figure that FY 2014-15 to 2017-18 has not been reached at desired level in term of equity of the organization.

Profit Analysis of BEXIMCO

Model Description	
Model Name	MOD_3
Series or Sequence	1
Transformation	net_profit_beximco_tk_million
Non-Seasonal Differencing	None
Seasonal Differencing	0
Length of Seasonal Period	0
Horizontal Axis Labels	No periodicity
Intervention Onsets	Date_
Reference Lines	None
Area Below the Curve	None
	Not filled

Applying the model specifications from MOD_3

Case Processing Summary

		net_profit_beximco_tk_million
Series or Sequence Length		5
Number of Missing Values in the Plot	User-Missing	0
	System-Missing	0

Figure 11: Net profit Trend of BEXIMCO during FY 2013-14 to 2017-18
Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

In the figure 11, net profit (Tk. in million) of BEXIMCO has been shown for the FY 2013-14 to 2017-18. The figure shows that FY 2013-14 BEXIMCO has net profit Tk. 40,000 million (forty thousand million) but gradually it lost its profitability. Consequently, from the FY 2014-15 to 2017-18 FY it has been carrying negative profitability. It seems to be very insignificant and poor financial performances over the years for its shareholders and also for

the economy. Though financial statements very often shows that a big amount of profit has been utilizing for the development of organization as a result it becomes losing organization. On the other hand, government has been consistently subsidizing the organization over the periods to run it smoothly.

Equity Analysis of BEXIMCO

Model Description	
Model Name	MOD_4
Series or Sequence	1 shareholders_equity_beximco_tk_million
Transformation	None
Non-Seasonal Differencing	0
Seasonal Differencing	0
Length of Seasonal Period	No periodicity
Horizontal Axis Labels	Date_
Intervention Onsets	None
Reference Lines	None
Area Below the Curve	Not filled

Applying the model specifications from MOD_4

Case Processing Summary

		shareholders_equity_beximco_tk_million
Series or Sequence Length		5
Number of Missing Values in the Plot	User-Missing	0
	System-Missing	0

Figure 12: Change in Equity of BEXIMCO during FY 2013-14 to 2017-18
Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

Like in the figure 12, equity (Tk. in million) of BEXIMCO also has been seen as declining trend in the observed years. The figure 3 has been shown the equity of shareholders for the FY 2013-14 to 2017-18. It shows that FY 2013-14 BEXIMCO has equity Tk. 2,50,000 million (two lac fifty million) but in the FY 2014-15 it came down to Tk. 1,00,000 (one lac million). It has been found in the figure that FY 2014-15 to 2017-18 has not been reached at desired level in term of equity of the organization.

Profit Analysis of SQUARE

Model Description

Model Name	MOD_5
Series or Sequence	1
Transformation	net_profit_square_tk_million
Non-Seasonal Differencing	None
Seasonal Differencing	0
Length of Seasonal Period	No periodicity
Horizontal Axis Labels	Date_
Intervention Onsets	None
Reference Lines	None
Area Below the Curve	Not filled

Applying the model specifications from MOD_5

Case Processing Summary

		net_profit_square_tk_million
Series or Sequence Length		5
Number of Missing Values in the Plot	User-Missing	0
	System-Missing	0

Figure 13: Net profit Trend of SQUARE during FY 2013-14 to 2017-18
Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

In the figure 13, net profit (Tk. in million) of SQUARE has been shown for the FY 2013-14 to 2017-18. The figure shows that FY 2013-14 SQUARE has net profit Tk. 40,000 million (forty thousand million) but gradually it lost its profitability. Consequently, from the FY 2014-15 to 2017-18 FY it has been carrying negative profitability. It seems to be very insignificant and poor financial performances over the years for its shareholders and also for the economy. Though financial statements very often shows that a big amount of profit has been utilizing for the development of organization as a result it becomes losing organization. On the other hand, government has been consistently subsidizing the organization over the periods to run it smoothly.

Equity Analysis of SQUARE

Model Description

Model Name	MOD_6	
Series or Sequence	1	shareholders_equity_square_tk_million
Transformation	None	
Non-Seasonal Differencing		0
Seasonal Differencing		0
Length of Seasonal Period	No periodicity	
Horizontal Axis Labels	Date_	
Intervention Onsets	None	
Reference Lines	None	
Area Below the Curve	Not filled	

Applying the model specifications from MOD_6

Case Processing Summary

		shareholders_equity_square_tk_million
Series or Sequence Length		5
Number of Missing Values in the Plot	User-Missing	0
	System-Missing	0

Figure 14: Change in Equity of SQUARE during FY 2013-14 to 2017-18
Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

Like in the figure 14, equity (Tk. in million) of SQUARE also has been seen as declining trend in the observed years. The figure 3 has been shown the equity of shareholders for the FY 2013-14 to 2017-18. It shows that FY 2013-14 SQUARE has equity Tk. 2,50,000 million (two lac fifty million) but in the FY 2014-15 it came down to Tk. 1,00,000 (one lac million). It has been found in the figure that FY 2014-15 to 2017-18 has not been reached at desired level in term of equity of the organization.

Profit and Equity Forecasting of ACI, BEXIMCO and SQUARE for 2018-22

Model Description			Model Type
Model ID	net_profit_aci_tk_million	Model_1	ARIMA(0,0,0)
	shareholders_equity_aci_t k_million	Model_2	Holt
	net_profit_beximco_tk_m illion	Model_3	Holt
	shareholders_equity_bexi mco_tk_million	Model_4	Holt
	net_profit_square_tk_mill ion	Model_5	Holt
	shareholders_equity_squa re_tk_million	Model_6	Holt

Model Summary

Fit Statistic	Model Fit										
	Mean	SE	Minimum	Maximum	Percentile						
					5	10	25	50	75	90	95
Stationary R-squared	.682	.342	2.220E-16	.956	2.220E-16	2.220E-16	.543	.795	.854	.956	.956
R-squared	.677	.356	2.220E-16	.995	2.220E-16	2.220E-16	.440	.819	.879	.995	.995
RMSE	1224.827	763.643	183.920	2439.227	183.920	183.920	676.046	1115.923	1850.219	2439.227	2439.227
MAPE	30.444	55.282	1.429	142.826	1.429	1.429	2.558	10.509	46.551	142.826	142.826
MaxAPE	81.857	156.399	3.391	400.196	3.391	3.391	5.223	23.813	125.620	400.196	400.196
MAE	783.562	512.220	106.763	1648.476	106.763	106.763	401.544	754.791	1114.678	1648.476	1648.476
MaxAE	1778.522	1086.798	286.732	3380.465	286.732	286.732	976.954	1616.123	2768.614	3380.465	3380.465
Normalized BIC	14.321	1.776	11.073	16.243	11.073	11.073	13.351	14.517	15.660	16.243	16.243

Table 24: Time Series Modeler Composite Statistics for ACI, BEXIMCO and SQUARE
Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

In the table 24, Time Series Modeler Composite Statistics for ACI, BEXIMCO and SQUARE have been presented. Overall statistics of all the organizations for financial forecasting is satisfactory for the shareholders as there are almost healthy or positive scenarios in the model statistics value like Stationary R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, MaxAPE, MAE, MaxAE, Normalized BIC etc. though there are a little ups and downs in the equities of organizations. Stability is concerned; the organizations are in good shape in terms of financial performances.

Forecast

Model		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
net_profit_aci_tk_million- Model_1	Forecast	1020.400	1020.400	1020.400	1020.400	1020.400
	UCL	4038.594	4038.594	4038.594	4038.594	4038.594
	LCL	-1997.794	-1997.794	-1997.794	-1997.794	-1997.794
shareholders_equity_aci_tk_mil- lion-Model_2	Forecast	15658.816	17664.014	19669.212	21674.411	23679.609
	UCL	20922.208	23158.563	25385.579	27604.303	29815.602
	LCL	10395.423	12169.465	13952.846	15744.518	17543.616
net_profit_beximco_tk_million- Model_3	Forecast	1518.519	1737.386	1956.254	2175.121	2393.989
	UCL	2103.836	2348.355	2591.843	2834.415	3076.166
	LCL	933.202	1126.417	1320.664	1515.827	1711.811
shareholders_equity_beximco_t k_million-Model_4	Forecast	64813.031	67970.385	71127.740	74285.095	77442.450
	UCL	72575.740	76075.455	79561.285	83034.793	86497.271
	LCL	57050.321	59865.316	62694.196	65535.397	68387.629
net_profit_square_tk_million- Model_5	Forecast	8600.181	9405.627	10211.073	11016.518	11821.964
	UCL	12243.362	13120.815	13996.901	14871.695	15745.266
	LCL	4957.000	5690.439	6425.244	7161.342	7898.662
shareholders_equity_square_tk_ million-Model_6	Forecast	53221.837	59413.175	65604.514	71795.852	77987.190
	UCL	55895.373	62382.720	68843.354	75283.469	81707.183
	LCL	50548.301	56443.631	62365.673	68308.235	74267.197

For each model, forecasts start after the last non-missing in the range of the requested estimation period, and end at the last period for which non-missing values of all the predictors are available or at the end date of the requested forecast period, whichever is earlier.

Table 25: Net Profit and Equity Forecasting for 2018-22 of ACI, BEXIMCO and SQUARE
Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

The table 25 represents the forecasting of net profit and equity for the FY 2018-19 to FY 2022-23 of ACI, BEXIMCO and SQUARE. From the first two rows of the table represents ACI's forecasting of net profit and equity for next five years respectively. It shows mentionable stability of financial performances of the organization. On the other hand, performances of BEXIMCO in terms of net profit represent also consistent and upward which may continue over the years. To end with, SQUARE has also good scenarios as net profits may go up most of the periods.

Figure 15: Net Profit and Equity Forecasting for 2018-22 of ACI, BEXIMCO and SQUARE
 Source: SPSS Data Analysis Output

The figure 15 represents the forecasting of net profit and equity for the FY 2018-19 to FY 2022-23 of ACI, BEXIMCO and SQUARE. The different curves like red color presents observed value and blue presents forecasting value of selected government organizations. From the first two portions of the figure represents ACI's observed and forecasting net profit and equity for last five years and next five years respectively. In the observed curve (red) does not show somehow stability of the organization though constant scenarios in forecasting curve (blue). On the other side, BEXIMCO's observed curve shows consistent higher efficient performances over the years as forecasting follows the same trend of the organization. Last but not the least, SQUARE has high level of increasing in net profits over the observed periods and forecasting curve also takes place similar things in the following years. Its equity has got better trend in the forecasting periods.

Chapter: 6

**RECOMMENDATION &
ETHICAL ISSUES**

6.1 RECOMMENDATION ON FINDINGS

Hypotheses have been tested through multiple regression method using SPSS. The results show that organizational growth certainly depends on employees' productivity and financial performance for both public and private sector organizations. In addition, time series analyses have been undertaken using SPSS to know the current situation and forecast financial condition of public and private organizations for next five years. Results show that public organizations financial condition more volatile, there are huge ups and downs in the financial performances over the years. Next five years financial forecasting also suggests that consistent ups and downs will be there and government may have to subsidize consistently those organizations during the years. On the other hand time series data analyses result show that private organizations have been doing well in terms of their financial performances. Besides financial forecasting for the following five years also suggests that consistent upward trend to be found in terms of their financial activities. While conducting this research public organizations employee were reluctant to provide their responses, dissimilarly private organizations employees were found to be interested to response properly on the questionnaire survey by the researchers.

6.2 ETHICAL ISSUES DURING AND AFTER FIELDWORK

The basic rule in any research field is causing no harm to any of the research participants including the principal researcher, informants and other field assistants. In order to carry out field work in such settings, ethical issues of personal security should be considered from the very beginning when developing research design and methods. In order to avoid probable bias, attempts will be made to maintain a level of objectivity at all stages of the research. We shall be well aware of potential bias before conducting my fieldwork. To avoid possible data distortion, all the interviews will be recorded with the permission of the interviewees. To follow the research ethics, permission will be granted before taking pictures.

We shall assure the respondents that we shall not reveal their names neither in any newspaper nor in my research paper. We shall also assure them that their symbolic names may be used for research purpose. But for research ethics, we shall prefer not to mention any names of the research participants while writing our research report.

Chapter: 7
CONCLUSION

7.0 CONCLUSION

This research uncovers the impact of human resources on productivity and financial performances towards organizational growth. It allows comparative analyses and findings on Bangladeshi public and private organizations employees' contribution towards respective organizations. By the analyses and findings it reveals that employees of private organizations more consistent, efficient performer on productivity and financial aspects though there are some issues to be addressed like working hours, leaves, promotion and rewards, job security etc. by the stockholders to minimize agency gap. On the other hand, employees of the government organizations enjoy job security, regular promotion and rewards, fixed working hours etc. but still observed organizations employees well behind in terms of productivity and financial performances. Currently government takes inclusive training and development with full digitalization facilities especially for the government employees to enrich their skills and motivate themselves to work for the organization to contribute efficiently in productivity and profitability. Finally, this research can be evidence for the policymakers, researchers and private and public sector organizations toward realizing the significant impact of employees' contributions, involvement, and development of skills for financial growth of the organizations.

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